

DISTENDER D2.1: Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework

D2.1: Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework
WP 2, T 2.1, T2.2

Authors:

Sergeja Praper Gulič (UIRS), Barbara Goličnik Marušić (UIRS); Eglė Kalašnikovaitė (SC), Ieva Girdvainienė (SC), Andrius Jaržemskis (SC), Kasper Kok (WUR), Jay Marisca Gietzelt (WUR)

Reviewers: Kamila Stroinska (ITTI), Karolina Pieniowska (ITTI)

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v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	14/12/2022	SC	A. Jaržemskis; I. Girdvainienė; E. Kalašnikovaitė
2.0	04/01/2023	UIRS	B. Goličnik Marušuč, S. Praper Gulič

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3.0	25/01/2023	SC, UIRS	S. Praper Gulič, B. Goličnik Marušuč, E. Kalašnikovaitė, I. Girdvainienė
4.0		UIRS, SC, WUR	S. Praper Gulič, B. Goličnik Marušuč, E. Kalašnikovaitė, I. Girdvainienė, A. Jaržemskis, J. M. Gietzelt, K. Kok

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Meaning
AF	Project Application Form
CCS	Core case study
CEI	Community Engagement Index
DSS	Decision support system
FCS	Following case study
GHG	Greenhouse gas
MCA	Multi-criteria analysis
PMP	Project Management Plan
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
SH	Stakeholder
SSP	Shared Socio-economic Pathways
UCD	User centred design
WP	Work package

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0 Introduction

D2.1 is a document resulting from some of the activities run in T2.1 and T2.2. In the application form, Task 2.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping is described as follows: “A thorough understanding of the potential end-user network structures across Europe and especially in the case studies will be developed by identifying, mapping, analyzing and contacting the relevant groups and individuals involved in decision-making related to climate adaptation and mitigation”. Task 2.2 Co-creation methods and activities is described as follows: “Stakeholder engagement within DISTENDER will employ a ‘co-design-test-transfer’ approach that supports active stakeholder and societal engagement in the end-user needs analysis, co-designing explorative scenarios and normative integrated strategies, the iterative application and testing of the tools, data and knowledge within the DSS and the transfer of the DSS to broader stakeholder communities at regional, national and European levels.” While the T2.1 ends within the period of D2.1 preparation, T 2.2 has recently started and will continue until January 2025, within the context of WP2, the Deliverable D.2.1 fully covers the activities of T2.1 and reflects on the initial activities of T.2.2.

TASK	Year 1: Jun. 22 – May 23	Year 2: Jun. 23 – May 24	Year 3: Jun. 24 – May 25	Year 4:- Nov. 25
2.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping	D 2.1			
2.2 Co-creation methods and activities	D 2.2, D 2.3			
2.3 Evaluation of the engagement & building cap	D 2.4			

Figure 1: Context of D.2.1 within all the tasks of WP2

Actual implementation of activities in T2.1 is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Timeline of T2.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping

Actual implementation of activities in T2.2 as well as planned steps until the next deliverable (D2.2) is shown in figure 3.

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Figure 3: Timeline of T2.2 Co-creation methods and activities until D2.2

0.1 Methodology of work

This section shows the principles of work in WP2, focusing on the concept of co-working followed within and between DISTENDER partners (i.e., inner circle stakeholders). In principle, preparatory activities that include a review of the basic documents such as Project Application Form (AF), Project Management Plan (PMP), and the like, set up the structure and working steps accordingly. Thus, the basis for further collaborative process is provided. The initial working steps are mostly in the form of “informal” e-bilateral or e-thematic-focused discussions. Whereas when subjects addressed are well framed and issues clearly defined, “formal” discussions in a form of webinars or other appropriate e-supported meetings take place.

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Figure 4: Schematic diagram showing principles of work in WP2

Following that concept there were the following key steps taken:

1. In line with the AF and the Project Management Plan, to start with stakeholder identification, a special excel table was created calling a wishlist, where Project Partners (according to the instructions given) provided the stakeholders they imagine would be relevant for the project.
2. The wishlist was circulated and in several bilateral meetings discussed. Project Partners were advised how to approach (further).
3. In the meantime an informal thematic-focused discussion was set up to present some intermediated analysis of the wishlists and discuss open questions.
4. When intermediate results about stakeholder identification and mapping were available, a Progress Report was provided and shared at the DISTENDER sharepoint, so everyone got a chance to get familiar with the ongoing work.
5. Further a special focus was paid to stakeholder as end user of DSS (decision support system). A joint WP2-WP8 webinar was organised. This takes a form of a "formal" meeting, dedicated to DISTENDER partners, where the attendees received the preparation materials in advance, and where work was moderated also in breakout rooms.

Based on the knowledge gathered upon conceptual approach towards stakeholder identification (wishlist analysis) and other collected general information about the stakeholders and CCSs readiness for participatory activities (D9.1) shifts towards possible methodological approaches for actual participatory activities were made.

For further work to complete D2.1, the following steps were relevant:

1. Study of participation and co-creation related contents in the DISTENDER AF to get an overview of such contents and understand the baseline for participation and co-creation in the project.
2. Study relation of T2.1 and T2.2 to work packages, activities and other deliverables to create a roadmap of D2.1 contents and insights for the overarching co-creation approach.
3. Discuss possible implementation and open questions with CCSs (“informal” and “formal” e-bilateral or e-focused groups communication) to get further insights about practical options as well as the basis for optimal framework proposal and co-produce co-creation plan for DISTENDER participatory activities.

0.2 Structure of the document

The document is composed of three main parts. Part 1 Background information refers to key participation and co-creation related contents in the DISTENDER application form, and summarises on the relations between work packages, activities and deliverables of relevance for participation and co-creation, to frame the background of the content and context of D2.1. Part 2 Stakeholder identification and mapping is mostly referring to results obtained within the T2.1, whereas Part 3 Co-creation framework is dedicated to completed and planned activities of T.2.2.

In detail, part 2 of the D2.1 contains two major sections related to stakeholder identification and mapping, where:

- a) Methodology section – a part where the concept of stakeholders (SHs) is explained, their identification and mapping detailed, elaborated on how these activities were done and evident implications and limitations listed.
- b) The second part of the document dives deeper into the core case studies (CCSs) and the rest of the inner SHs (inner partners of the DISTENDER) by presenting the insights gathered from analyzing the data from the wishlists that were filled out and provided by the representatives of the CCSs and the rest of the inner partners. The section covers such topics as general overview of SHs, the distribution of stakeholders according to their interest and influence, SH distribution according to the SH engagement matrix and a review on the listed SH engagement nuances.

In detail, part 3 of the D.2.1 contains six parts related to co-creation framework, where:

- a) Firstly, relevant definitions are presented.
- b) The Conceptual DISTENDER model for stakeholder identification and engagement presents the framework for the SH identification and mapping through the future work of the CCSs in the project to be able to identify, list and map SHs themselves and maintain their SH wishlist updated, as well as manage the communication.

- c) Co-creation approaches in relation to three key DISTENDER participatory driven activities are introduced, specifically for socio-economic scenarios, adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies, and for the decision support system.
- d) Overview of case studies participatory experiences summarises upon case studies' experiences and familiarity with co-creative and participatory approaches and stakeholders' engagement, as revealed in the document D9.1 Case studies.
- e) DISTENDER co-creation concept is described and graphically presented.
- f) Co-creation plan over the key participatory related WPs is outlined.

1 Background information

This chapter refers to some basic starting points for the work and gives an overview of the participation and co-creation related contents from the application form. It also provides a review of relations of work packages which foresee any form of participation and co-creation, including proposed activities and deliverables of relevance for participation and co-creation.

1.1 Participation and co-creation related content in the DISTENDER application form

To create a baseline for the DISTENDER co-creation approach and framework, firstly an analysis of the DISTENDER application form was performed. This chapter first shows an overview of the participation and co-creation related content. The information has been organised in thematic subchapters, namely general background, co-creation and stakeholder engagement, conceptions of socio-economic scenarios, adaptation/mitigation integrated strategies, the concept and role of decision support system. Each section is summed up with key underlying principles or concepts. Second, the collection of concepts and approaches is finally commented and summarised, so the initial intentions and insights of the project are considered as the basic input. This also means that no rounded off participation/co-creation “story” has been aimed for, and the picture that emerges may appear rather imbalanced and patchy. The principle of work was to extract, from the rather complicated and conceptually partly overloaded text of the application form (parts), the information and statements referring to participation/co-creation and their relation to other key project themes.

1.1.1 Overview of the participation and co-creation related content

In the current chapter, information about co-creation and participation from the DISTENDER application form part B, chapters 1. Excellence and 2. Impact is summarized. The intention is to present an overview of the initial ideas regarding co-creation and participation as “enshrined” in the project application form. This is part of the background for defining the co-creation approach. An analysis of the application form text was performed, and potentially relevant parts extracted and summed up.

1.1.1.1 General

A general premise stated in the DISTENDER application form is that *integrating mitigation and adaptation with stakeholder participation*¹ may help to avoid locking a city, region or nation into inefficient or counterproductive infrastructures and policies. A further assumption is that climate action plans should *integrate top-down and bottom-up approaches* in

¹ In the chapter, important statements, concepts or keywords from the DISTENDER application form are presented *in Italics*.

synergistic ways. In view of this, the intention is to construct in the project a *methodological framework to guide the integration of climate adaptation and mitigation through participatory approaches*.

It is claimed that conducting vulnerability assessments, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions inventories, and scenario analysis is *by definition inter-sectoral, multi-scale and participatory*. These three elements are the base of the DISTENDER methodology. As key concepts the understanding of the synergies, conflicts and trade-offs between mitigation and adaptation strategies and *facilitating informed and participatory decision making* are mentioned.

The methodology will be tested in case studies and supported by a *high level of stakeholder involvement and integration with those responsible for the implementation of policies, and those impacted by their implementation*.

Flexible and participatory planning processes are thought to be required to adapt holistic approaches to mitigation and adaptation to the context-specific situation. It is expected that such proceeding will ensure legitimate and salient action carried by all *important stakeholders*.

A large number of private and public bodies (local, regional and/or national) shall be given the opportunity to participate in the project activities and explore innovative adaptation and mitigation plans or re-evaluate the planned/implemented actions considering all the synergies and trade-offs.

One of the ambitions of the DISTENDER project consortium is *to incorporate social and behavioural factors through stakeholders' engagement* (project objective O1) because future planning actions are expected to involve behavioural changes.

In data-collection, co-creation techniques and user-related methods, e.g., focus groups and behaviour mapping in socio-economic scenarios, will be used for obtaining small data.

Keywords/principles/concepts:

- integrating top-down and bottom-up approaches
- flexible and participatory planning process
- co-creation techniques, user-related methods

1.1.1.2 Co-creation and stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement process and participation using co-creation (WP2): Different target groups (at least 5) will be involved to address the requirements for a wide range of stakeholders within case studies. The *stakeholder-driven methodology* will be applied for

creating socio-economic scenarios, integrated strategies and discovering synergies and trade-offs of the adaptation and mitigation strategies (project objective O1).

In the DISTENDER application form part related to methodology, the following topics are considered:

- *In-depth, continuous processes of engagement and empowerment through community-driven solutions*, knowledge acquisition, climate change communication. *Workshops, on-line platforms, social media.*
- *Community participation and co-creation: Citizens and stakeholders taking part in a collaborative process with consortium partners.* Creating effective multifunctional solutions that promote ownership and social cohesion. Increasing *community participation in adaptation planning.*
- Stakeholders participate in the process of deciding what futures are considered. *Experimentation, learning, building shared meaning.* Plans begin to gain agreement from the outset.
- Use of *participatory techniques to support open discussion* for co-development of exploratory scenarios and adaptation/mitigation integrated strategies.
- *Community based methods* – social participation, citizen action as tools for a fair and effective implementation of adaptation/mitigation policies/strategies.
- *Community engagement* (and co-creation): Citizen involvement in decision support system and local scenario development, other forms of participation: *public consultations, meeting of civic associations, co-design workshops.*
- *Community readiness*: the degree to which a community is ready to take action on an issue, in a specific, dimensional, and stratified way. An analysis of community efforts, knowledge of efforts, leadership, willingness, knowledge, and resources needs to be performed to assess community readiness.
- *Significant stakeholder engagement*: long-term involvement, commitment, participation (active contributions to dialogue). Needed to develop integrated strategies to be adopted by communities. Complexities and conflicts to be explored and negotiated.
- *Evaluating* the involvement of key stakeholder groups, impact of stakeholders on the process and decisions. Evaluation of engagement and participatory processes by quantitative and qualitative factors.

The subchapter *Gender dimension* promises that in DISTENDER

- the gender-analysis will be integrated during the whole project lifecycle by, among other, integrating women's skills, knowledge and capacities and *supporting the co-creation of action aimed at improving education, health and wellbeing through mitigation and adaptation to climate change,*
- the *gender aspect* will be taken into account *in stakeholder selection,* and
- the *co-creation process* will be *evaluated taking into account quantitative factors* such as gender balance.

Keywords/principles/concepts:

- collaborative process stakeholders – consortium partners
- community participation and co-creation
- stakeholder-driven methodology
- participatory techniques (for open discussion)
- community readiness
- evaluation of engagement and participatory processes

1.1.1.3 Socio-economic scenarios

Participatory development of localized socio-economic scenarios (WP3): A set of local socio-economic scenarios will be developed by stakeholders, facilitated by the combination of bottom-up participatory methodology in combination with top-down approaches. Particular attention will be devoted to *vulnerable categories inclusion and avoiding the gender gap* (project objective O2).

In the AF chapter on methodology, subchapter *Context-specific socio-economic scenarios*, the following co-creation/participation related information is given:

- Stakeholders will be involved to examine the integrated strategies, to select a specific one to be seen as the most probable, to specify the local deviations and the expected impact at the context-specific scale.
- A novel methodology will be developed for creating an integrated set of climate and socio-economic scenarios covering the local scale and key sectors of the case studies. The basis are the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) and Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs). *Scenarios will be stakeholder-driven and stakeholder-relevant* driven by the *primary decision-makers in the case studies*, which include local, national, EU, sectoral, public, and private decision-makers.
- The *Story-And-Simulation approach* as an *overarching framework* to iteratively link the qualitative, participatory SSP storylines for the local case studies to the quantitative impact models.
- *A high degree of stakeholder involvement*. Use of a *structured multi-scale approach* to produce sets of scenarios consistent and coherent across a range of spatial and sectoral scales. *Co-creating case-study-specific socio-economic scenarios* nested within the European SSPs, which in turn are nested within the global SSPs.

Keywords/principles/concepts:

- story and simulation approach
- integrating bottom-up knowledge with top-down information
- stakeholder-driven and stakeholder-relevant (scenarios)
- primary decision makers
- vulnerable categories (of stakeholders)
- gender gap
- professionally facilitated participatory processes

1.1.1.4 Adaptation/mitigation integrated strategies

Robust adaptation and mitigation actions and policies from a suite of harmonized strategies constructed through participatory methods (WP6): The project will work with stakeholders to develop visions of their ideal future and work backwards from these taking into consideration the opportunities and constraints when combining adaptation and mitigation options from existing policy and practice (project objective O5).

A broad community of stakeholders (decision-makers and other non-academic actors) will be involved in co-creating a suite of harmonized adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies.

Stakeholder and public involvement are required for legitimacy and for gathering the necessary knowledge to tackle different problems appropriately. This is a precondition for successful adaptation or mitigation strategies.

The whole ecosystem of stakeholders, ranging from industry and businesses, policy makers and academia to local communities and NGOs, will be engaged to catalyse mitigation actions at national and regional scales.

The chapter on methodology, subchapter *Integration of adaptation and mitigation strategies*, contains the following co-creation/participation related topics:

- *Co-developing with stakeholders multiple base scenarios* to be used for a robustness check for the pathways considering adaptation and mitigation options.
- *Stakeholder-led approach, working with end-users.* Co-developing visions of a desirable climate-resilient future. Co-generating a range of adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies through a range of iterative steps. Producing more robust, context-relevant, and credible insights for decision-making, increasing the legitimacy and acceptance of the development trajectories needed to achieve the vision.

Keywords/principles/concepts:

- community of stakeholders: decision makers and other non-academic actors
- ecosystem of stakeholders: industry, businesses, policy makers, academia, local communities, NGOs
- stakeholder-led approach
- working with end-users

1.1.1.5 Decision support system (DSS)

In the subchapter *Cost-benefit evaluation and DSS* of the DISTENDER AF chapter on methodology it is stated that:

- The decision support system will be *addressed to various stakeholders*. This should be a flexible, user-friendly, yet comprehensive platform, employing advanced techniques. A *co-creation process* will be employed, and *key stakeholders engaged to determine the design and supported functions* of the DSS.
- A *user centred design approach (UCD)* is to be followed in the software design process. The approach encompasses *gathering information about end users* in the early stage of work, *involving end users from the beginning of the process*, as well as *testing user experience* during implementation phase.

Keywords/principles/concepts:

- user centred design approach (UCD)
- end users as target group/stakeholders

1.1.1.6 Other

Ambitions of the DISTENDER project partnership include among other:

- the co-creation process will allow businesses and investors, local decision makers, social and environmental NGOs to identify adequate solutions with project team,
- through the *co-creative multi-stakeholder approach*, stakeholders will get the opportunity to expand their knowledge around climate change impacts, adaptation and mitigation actions, and identify synergies, trade-off, opportunities, drivers and barriers of the strategies implementation.

The application form chapter on methodology, subchapter *Impact assessment models* mentions *serious games* as a tool to address and communicate with the stakeholders the potential of coordinated actions to answer the challenges of climate adaptation and mitigation.

In the subchapter on *Cost-benefit evaluation and decision support system (DSS)* it is stated that:

- to provide legitimacy to the multi-criteria analysis (MCA), there is a strong need for stakeholder's inclusion in the assessment process, and
- the *range of case studies* studied in *close engagement with policy, investment and business actors* will provide concrete insights into the costs of climate change and recommendations for cost-effective, robust and resilient responses for key European sectors and policy domains.

The subchapter *Case studies* covers two co-creation related aspects:

- A *community of stakeholders* will be formed by the case studies. They will engage in peer-to-peer learning and capacity building among core case studies and follower case studies, as well as knowledge exchange and transfer.

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- For the case study North-east of The Netherlands it is planned to co-produce integrated strategies with stakeholders from multiple sectors and scales which will allow for the inclusion of multiple knowledge frames.

The subchapter *Open science* offers the premise that DISTENDER grounds on more collaborative, interdisciplinary, open, transparent and reproducible science. Insights about *scientific co-creation with end-users* will be gathered and *such co-creation favoured through open innovation*.

Among the DISTENDER pathways toward impact, producing *tools with different complexity to facilitate the participation of stakeholders with different background* is mentioned. The tools are expected to range from simple observations to complex analyses, from smartphone-based observation guidelines to model analysis.

In the subchapter *Other expected impacts*, it is declared that the project's stakeholder engagement process is aiming at *long-term participation between key actors, social learning*, as well as *behavioural change of involved stakeholders*.

The subchapter on *Measures to maximise impact* declares that the project's dissemination strategy will be designed in such a way as to engage stakeholders who will use the project results (in coordination with WPs 2 and 6). Further, the *analysis of stakeholder needs and mapping (carried out in WP2) in relation to their role and level of involvement* will be used as part of methodology for definition of the communication and dissemination strategy. To monitor and measure the impacts and effectiveness of the strategy, a set of indicators and indexes will be applied. One of them is the *Community Engagement Index (CEI)*. Its function is to *measure the actual stakeholders' engagement with the project*.

Finally, in the subchapter on *measuring and monitoring the impacts*, it is declared that evaluation of the project's effectiveness will be based on key impact indicators. Participatory processes, more specifically focus group discussions with stakeholders (local authorities, civil society representatives, and other relevant stakeholders), will be applied to define the indicators. The latter will target the central objectives of the project: mitigating climate change, strengthening adaptation, and increasing resilience to climate change induced risks.

Keywords/principles/concepts:

- scientific co-creation with end-users
- co-creative multi-stakeholder approach
- community of stakeholders (core and follower case studies)
- tools to facilitate participation of stakeholders with different backgrounds
- serious games
- community engagement index

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1.1.2 Summary and conclusions

The above compilation of the co-creation and participation related content from chapters 1. Excellence and 2. Impact of the DISTENDER application form does not give a consistent “story”. It is much rather a collection of concepts and approaches which are elaborated in more detail and more systematically presented in chapter 3. *Quality and efficiency of implementation*, subchapter 3.1 *Work plan and resources*. A short summary and some conclusions of the analysis are presented below.

1.1.2.1 General

Stakeholder participation is denoted as one of the key components of the DISTENDER project. Namely, the aim is to construct a methodological framework to guide integrating adaptation and mitigation through participatory approaches. Furthermore, understanding of the synergies, conflicts and trade-offs between mitigation and adaptation strategies, and facilitating informed and participatory decision making are pointed out as the key concepts of DISTENDER.

The need or intention to implement co-creation and/or participation is indicated for practically all project’s main thematic fields: socio-economic scenarios, adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies, cost-benefit evaluation, decision support system, case studies, communication and dissemination. It is also claimed that conducting vulnerability assessments and GHG emissions inventories is participatory by definition.

Beside contributing to the main thematic fields, there is a number of specific subjects and aims that will be supported by participatory activities, such as:

- to incorporate social and behavioural factors through stakeholder engagement and address behavioural changes,
- use of co-creation techniques and user-related methods in data collection for obtaining small data,
- building up long term participation between key actors, social learning and behavioural change of involved stakeholders.

1.1.2.2 Stakeholders

With reference to stakeholders, one common attribute is that different societal groups are referred to in connection with co-creation and project’s participatory activities. When it comes to which groups should be involved, there is less uniformity. Some examples are:

- at least five different target groups
- those responsible for implementation of policies, and those impacted by their implementation
- local, national, EU, sectoral, public, and private decision-makers
- local, regional and/or national private and public bodies

D2.1: D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework WP 2, T2.1, 22
T2.2

- industry, businesses, policy makers, academia, local communities, NGOs
- businesses, investors, local decision makers, social and environmental NGOs.

Beside *stakeholders*, other terms are used as well, such as *end-users*, *target groups*, or *actors*.

1.1.2.3 Approaches, methods and tools

Throughout the DISTENDER application form text, approaches, methods and tools are mentioned which the partners intend to use when working with stakeholders. They range from rather complex and elaborate to simpler ones. The former includes e. g. the story and simulation approach, the user centred design approach, behaviour mapping, public consultations. Other working methods and tools named are e. g. focus groups, workshops, meetings.

1.2 Relation of D2.1 to work packages, activities and other deliverables of relevance for participation and co-creation

The information presented in the chapter is taken from the DISTENDER application form part 3. *Quality and efficiency of the implementation*, and from the project management plan. An overview of the work packages, tasks, and deliverables related to participation and co-creation is given.

1.2.1 Participation and co-creation related work packages, and tasks

Descriptions of work packages containing explicit mentions of participatory and co-creation activities are *WP2 Co-creation and stakeholder engagement*, *WP3 Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios*, *WP6 Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies*, *WP8 Decision support system*, and *WP9 Case studies*.

1.2.1.1 WP2 Co-creation and stakeholder engagement

The overall aim of the work package is to coordinate and facilitate the DISTENDER co-creation approach. Its tasks relate to identification and mapping of stakeholders, co-creation methods and activities, and evaluation of stakeholder engagement. An overview of WP2 tasks is presented in the box below.

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WP 2 Co-creation and stakeholder engagement

The overall aim is to *coordinate and facilitate the DISTENDER co-creation approach*.

Task 2.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping

Identifying, mapping, analysing and contacting relevant groups and individuals involved in decision-making related to climate change adaptation and mitigation.

Task 2.2 Co-creation methods and activities

Employing the *co-design approach* for explorative scenarios and normative integrated strategies, and *co-design–test–transfer approach* in relation to the different phases of the decision support system development (end-user needs analysis, testing of the tools, data and knowledge, and transfer to broader stakeholder communities at regional, national and European levels).

The focus is on:

- *Co-creation activities for socio-economic scenarios*

Setup and application of the co-creation framework to co-develop socio-economic scenarios

- *Co-creation activities for co-design strategies*

Setup and application of the co-creation framework to co-design strategies

- *Co-creation activities to develop robust strategies*

Setup and application of the co-creation framework to develop robust strategies in the task T6.3 with a participatory process of stakeholders

Task 2.3 Evaluation of the engagement and building capacity

Establishing a monitoring system for the quality of stakeholder engagement in DISTENDER. Questionnaires and specific focus groups will be applied if needed.

WP2 is strongly connected with other work packages, which is reflected not only in its objective, but also in the definition of tasks. The latter connect it most strongly to WP3 (socio-economic scenarios), WP6 (strategies, robust strategies), and WP8 (decision support system).

1.2.1.2 WP3 Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios

In WP3, two tasks concern co-creation activities. Task 3.2 is about the design and flexible methodology to co-develop socio-economic scenarios. As the core method, participatory scenario workshops are named. The need for a flexible methodology is also highlighted, the reason being the diversity of case studies. A strong collaboration with T2.2 is envisaged.

Task 3.3 relates to co-development of socio-economic scenarios for all case studies, concerning implementation in each of the case studies.

WP3 Cross-scale consistent socio-economic scenarios

The overall objective is to develop cross-scale socio-economic scenarios to structure plausible future outlooks of crucial drivers for all case studies, and to integrate climatic and socio-economic developments. The overall approach is highly participatory and work done in close collaboration with WP2.

Task 3.2 Design, and flexible methodology to co-develop socio-economic scenarios

The core methods are participatory scenario development workshops – these can be either live events or online – all starting from the European SSPs as common ground. The diversity of case studies calls for a flexible methodology of which some elements are common, but others can be modified to fit case-study characteristics. To be done in strong collaboration with T2.2 to obtain consistent methodologies.

Task 3.3 Co-development of socio-economic scenarios

A set of socio-economic scenarios will be developed for all core case studies:

- *Case study 1* Austria (BMK)
- *Case study 2* The North-east of the Netherlands (HUAS)
- *Case study 3* Dehesas and montados (EURAF)
- *Case study 4* Guimaraes (GUIMARAES)
- *Case study 5* Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

1.2.1.3 WP6 Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies

Three of the four work package tasks comprise co-design related activities. Task 6.1 is about collecting contributions from relevant stakeholders with regard to adaptation and mitigation strategies. The methodologies and tools to do that should be defined in WP2. The task is related to co-design of the strategies for each of the case studies.

In task 6.2 *Assessment of adaptation and mitigation policies* a “strong co-creation element” is mentioned. Applying co-creation should serve to take appropriate account of the real world challenges that the case studies face with regard to integrating adaptation and mitigation options.

Finally, task 6.3 concerns integration of exploratory scenarios with the adaptation and mitigation options and policies. For each of the case studies, potentially robust strategies and policies will be identified in a participatory process. The task is related to the process for single case study.

WP6 Integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies

Task 6.1 Co-design the strategies

Collecting the contributions from the relevant stakeholders based on the methodologies and tools defined in WP2. We have to deal with strategies on adaptation and mitigation.

A set up of strategies will be described to the stakeholders as a preparation task.

The focus is on co-design the strategies for:

- *Case study 1* Austria (BMK)
- *Case study 2* The North-east of the Netherlands (HUAS)
- *Case study 3* Dehesas and montados (EURAF)
- *Case study 4* Guimaraes (GUIMARAES)
- *Case study 5* Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

Task 6.2 Assessment of adaptation and mitigation policies

Providing a review of current adaptation and mitigation strategies at a European scale and integrating this with strategies at the local scale and local challenges to their implementation in practice. Identifying and detailing the major synergies and opportunities between the policies and integration with assessments of key national policies and local priorities. A strong co-creation element will be needed to ensure that the real world challenges of integrating adaptation and mitigation options posed to the case studies are fully considered.

Task 6.3 Development of robust strategies

The integration of exploratory scenarios (as developed in WP3) with the identified adaptation and mitigation options and policies. In a participatory process, potentially robust strategies and policies will be identified for:

- *Case study 1* Austria (BMK)
- *Case study 2* The North-east of the Netherlands (HUAS)
- *Case study 3* Dehesas and montados (EURAF)
- *Case study 4* Guimaraes (GUIMARAES)
- *Case study 5* Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

1.2.1.4 WP8 Decision support system

In WP8, two tasks are related to engagement with stakeholders, that is task 8.1 *DSS requirements* and task 8.4 *DSS validation*. In the frame of the former, gathering of the DSS requirements by surveying the end users is envisaged. For the latter, validation of the first version of DSS and the final validation with end users is planned. In both cases, stakeholders are related with case studies. End users in the final validation include also potential users outside the case studies.

WP8 Decision support system

Task 8.1 DSS Requirements

DSS requirements will be gathered surveying the end users.

Task 8.4 DSS Validation

Validation and verification testing activities, conducted with the partner cities/regions and in broader dissemination activities, will follow at least two-steps process:

- Validation of the first version

Includes validation of the core and follower case studies with the aim to improve the first version of the DSS

- End users validation

A final evaluation of the DSS, presentation to core and follower case studies and other potential end users

1.2.1.5 WP9 Case studies

Participation and co-creation feature strongly in tasks of WP9. They are predominantly implementation oriented.

Firstly, they concern participation of the core (and follower) case studies to generate the future socio-economic scenarios. WP3 guidelines and WP 2 methodologies will be the base for implementing the participatory activities.

Secondly, they concern participation of the core (and follower) case studies to co-design mitigation and adaptation strategies is envisaged. Task 6.1 provides guidelines, and WP2 methodologies to be followed.

Finally, they describe participation of the core (and follower) case studies to co-design robust mitigation and adaptation strategies. Task 6.3 prepares guidelines, and WP2 methodologies to be followed.

WP9 Case studies

Task 9.1 Development and planning of the case studies

Planning, set-up and execution of the case studies will involve all relevant stakeholders, Workshops with EU-level and local end-users and stakeholders will be carried out in each case study identifying priorities for application of adaptation and mitigations strategies for each location.

The focus is on:

- Participation to co-develop socio-economic scenarios

Participation of the core and follower case studies to generate the future socio-economic scenarios based on WP3 guidelines and WP2 methodologies, applied with each case study:

- Case study 1 Austria (BMK)

- Case study 2 The North-east of the Netherlands (HUAS)

- Case study 3 Dehesas and montados (EURAF)

- Case study 4 Guimaraes (GUIMARAES)

- Case study 5 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

Task 9.3 Case studies results and evaluation

Also includes participation tasks (co-design and develop strategies) of the core case studies. The focus in on:

- *Participation to co-develop strategies*

Participation of the core and follower case studies to co-design mitigation and adaptation strategies based on T6.1 guidelines and applying WP2 methodologies, applied with each case study:

- *Case study 1 Austria (BMK)*
- *Case study 2 The North-east of the Netherlands (HUAS)*
- *Case study 3 Dehesas and montados (EURAF)*
- *Case study 4 Guimaraes (GUIMARAES)*
- *Case study 5 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)*

- *Participation to co-develop robust strategies*

Participation of the core and follower case studies to co-design robust mitigation and adaptation strategies based on T6.3 guidelines and applying WP2 methodologies, applied with each case study:

- *Case study 1 Austria (BMK)*
- *Case study 2 The North-east of the Netherlands (HUAS)*
- *Case study 3 Dehesas and montados (EURAF)*
- *Case study 4 Guimaraes (GUIMARAES)*
- *Case study 5 Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)*

1.2.2 Deliverables

Co-creation and participation are subject of several DISTENDER deliverables. An overview of such deliverables with indications about the envisaged content is in the box below.

D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework

Report identifying stakeholders, participatory methods and tools for the co-creation process.

D2.2 Co-creation approach report I

Report about the progress of implementation of the co-creation approach plan, implementation of innovation methods and tools, adaptations to the different contexts. Producing co-creation and stakeholder engagement framework showing relations among co-creation stages, activities, tasks of actors as a separate document.

D2.3 Co-creation approach report II

Report about the progress of implementation of the co-creation approach plan, implementation of innovation methods and tools, adaptations to the different contexts. Producing co-creation and stakeholder engagement framework showing relations among co-creation stages, activities, tasks of actors as a separate document.

D.2.3 Co-creation and engagement evaluation

Report about evaluation of the engagement and co-creation approach development.

D3.1 Methodology to develop case-study specific socio-economic scenarios

It will describe the process, approach, and methods used for co-creating socio-economic scenario narratives for the cases studies.

D6.1 Methodology to co-develop adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies. Description of the methodology used to produce the strategies and the definition and action plan of the strategies.

Apparently, there is need for coordination about the content of deliverables D2.1, D3.1 and D6.1 to avoid overlapping and inconsistencies.

1.2.3 Relations between work packages, tasks, and deliverables

Based on the content of subchapters 1.2.1 and 1.2.2, a scheme was developed to show the connections between the activities and outputs of the different DISTENDER work packages relating to co-creation. A rather complex picture resulted showing among other that up to three work packages with their tasks are involved in the implementation of participatory activities. Interconnected is also the production of deliverables of the concerned work packages, calling for close collaboration and exchange among partners to avoid doubling of content and gaps.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram showing relations between work packages and tasks.

2 Stakeholder identification and mapping

According to the DISTENDER project management plan, the purpose of task 2.1 is to identify and map stakeholders (SHs). This was intended to do through an attempt to understand potential end-user network structures across represented European locations.

In this chapter the methodology of the stakeholder listing, mapping and analysis are provided together with the implications and limitations. As the application form of the project underlines the importance of the core case studies, the greatest emphasis regarding the stakeholder identification and mapping was made purposefully on them, although the analysis of the rest of the inner SHs (the rest of the partners) is also presented.

2.1 Methodology

The stakeholders in the context of DISTENDER refer to the actors which have an interest in the project and can either affect it or be affected by its outcomes. In order to determine the appropriate principle for approaching stakeholders, they were assigned to the outer or inner circle.

Inner circle stakeholders are the DISTENDER project partners. They are those (person / organization who belongs to any actual DISTENDER case study or is a partner in the project) provided in the ECAS system.

Outer circle stakeholders are those, who are external to the project and are invited to provide their expertise as required by any DISTENDER partner or also might be the ones for whom the outcomes of DISTENDER are being structured (e.g., developers, municipality representatives etc.), see the figure 6.

Figure 6: General types of stakeholders

A wishlist is a template (see Annex 1) that has been created and structured according to a specific logic (see the subchapter “The parameters of the SH wishlist”). In general, SH wishlist is a blank document generated to capture the stakeholders. Moreover, it serves to register detailed but structured information related with SHs, such as their field of specialization, their importance level and involvement into the DISTENDER project level as well as identify, if there are any links between stakeholders and DISTENDER partners. According to the template (Annex 1) prepared by the WP2 team, project partners collected material related to their stakeholders and transferred it for further processing during the first few months of the project.

On 16th of June 2022 a document, also known as a stakeholder wishlist (Annex 1) was shared. With the use of the document, it was intended to gather as much information as possible from the project partners and to identify the main stakeholders of the project and their characteristics at least preliminarily.

Following the data gathered from the wishlists, the mapping stage was brought through as the stakeholders listed were set into separate scheme trees called SH maps. The SHs were grouped in accordance with the Stakeholder engagement matrix (see figure 7), depending on their interest and influence levels that were evaluated by the representatives who filled out the wishlists.

All the received SH wishlists were listed and mapped but as the application form of the DISTENDER project implies, the focus was put on the stakeholders of 5 core case studies as they are the key players in the project. Moreover, the data that was gathered for the

purpose to perform T2.1 primarily, is also useful for other work packages of the project, hence the SHs out of the interest of the CCSs, were also analysed and mapped.

Table 1: A link between the T2.1 and other tasks of the WPs of the DISTENDER project

	Description
WP3	<p>D3.1 – Methodology to develop case-study specific socio-economic scenarios. To describe the process, approach, and methods used for co-creating socio-economic scenario narratives for the case studies.</p> <p>The approach of WP3, as defined in the application form, is highly participatory and a work is ought to be done in close collaboration with WP2 regarding especially those activities of co-creation procedures described in the 2nd part of this document.</p>
WP6	<p>T6.1 – Co-design the strategies – to collect the contributions from the relevant stakeholders based on the methodologies and tools defined in WP2.</p> <p>WP6 combines the input from WP2 and WP3 and aims to use it in proposing strategy recommendations to maximize synergies and minimize trade-offs between the dual goals of climate impact reduction and atmospheric GHGs decline. The input from this document and WP2 in general will assist in identifying relevant SHs and choosing right methods and tools to use when working with them.</p>
WP8	<p>T8.1 – DSS Requirements – to gather DSS requirements by surveying the end users. WP8 generally aims to develop a Decision Support System (DSS) to support decision makers (mostly, the end-users) in developing adaptation planning process and mitigation strategies, integrating the outcomes of the various WPs in the DSS (including WP2). This document contributes to the activities of WP8 by assisting to identify the relevant SHs (mostly, the end-users) when conducting a survey for the DSS (which is already done).</p>
WP9	<p>T9.1 - Development and planning of the case studies – to plan, set-up and execute the case studies while involving all relevant stakeholders; workshops with EU-level and local end-users and stakeholders will be carried out in each case study. This document will contribute by assisting to identify relevant SHs of the CCSs that will be involved in the work of WP9.</p>

WP2 and a T2.1 are closely linked with whole DISTENDER project, especially with those WPs and tasks that are related with SHs and co-creation activities. As the T2.1 aims to help the partners (especially CCSs) identify their SHs, prepare them perform this themselves and propose the participatory methods and tools for the co-creation process, these topics are continued and implemented in these WPs: WP3, WP6, WP8 and WP9 (see table 1).

Moreover, stakeholders can be grouped in other different categories, even in the framework of DISTENDER, but they are always going to fall under the inner and outer circle concept.

For the initial SH mapping, such categories that allow to generalize within the framework of the entire project were chosen.

The structures mentioned are developed by identifying, mapping, analysing relevant groups and individuals involved in decision making related to the climate change adaptation and mitigation.

2.1.1 The parameters of the SH wishlist

In order to gather all the information necessary but at the same time to keep the data manageable, the partners of the project were asked to fill in a document called SH wishlist, specifying the aspects regarding the stakeholders as follows:

- field, being defined as field of specialisation of the SH and addressing orientation of the stakeholder regarding their form of functioning (e.g. governmental / municipal administration representative, NGO, science institution, etc.);
- whether it was contacted, addressing the exact ties with the stakeholders mentioned;
- contacts, referring to concrete e-addresses and/or phone numbers;
- type of information required, being defined as the sort of contribution of the stakeholders towards the DISTENDER project and its impact and addressing the aspect why the SHs could be beneficial or important to be addressed and listed in the SH wishlist (e.g. data provider, expertise, participation in CSs);
- role, stakeholders can be assigned from the pre-defined list of roles;²
- interest rate, referring to of the level of interest rates, the mentioned stakeholders can be assigned from the pre-defined list of interest rates;¹
- influence rate, referring to of the level of influence rates, the mentioned stakeholders can be assigned from the pre-defined list of influence rates.¹

At the same time partners were assigning listed SHs to the inner or outer circle.

When collected the wishlists, the stakeholder engagement matrix was used to classify the collected data. This matrix (see Figure 7) sets the distribution of the stakeholders according to their interest and the influence levels. Based on this matrix, the stakeholders are classified according to the four positions in the matrix: kept into account, kept informed, meeting their needs, and managed closely.

² the aspects may change during the course of the project and the values may be different depending on the situation

Figure 7: Stakeholder engagement matrix, following approach of Robert Newcombe³

The stakeholder engagement matrix is a well-used concept introduced by R. Newcombe and is closely commented in relation to development of conceptual DISTENDER model for stakeholder identification and engagement in chapter 3.2.2. This stakeholder engagement matrix is essentially proposed for the use as the initial methodological structure during internal SH identification practices and more general classification. It is suggested to follow the SH engagement matrix-based methodology as an internally applied approach to list, map and structure relevant stakeholders. In the DISTENDER project, another, more content-specific approach of SHs is also applied (e.g. in WP3) and is targeted to more concrete criteria according to the topic of co-creation activities and takes into account such aspects as SH sector (water, energy, agriculture and health), institutional affiliation (government, scientist, NGO, artist, business, citizen), demographics (age, gender, representation of vulnerable groups, etc.).

Taking into account the assessment of interest and impact of the stakeholders which were evaluated by the partners in their wishlists, a general indicator was derived for stakeholders listed. Although the accent is being put on those stakeholders, that should be managed closely as well as those whose needs need to be met, the rest groups of them shall not be ignored.

2.1.2 Implications and limitations

It was noticeable that the partners and case studies of the project initially had difficulties in identifying their stakeholders or understanding the purpose and the idea behind the SH

³ Newcombe, R. (2003). From client to project stakeholders: a stakeholder mapping approach. *Construction Management and Economics*, 21(8), 841–848. doi:10.1080/0144619032000072137

mapping process. The partners found it challenging to delve into the context of their represented task (e.g. case study) and clarification what level of stakeholder involvement and what spectrums of the stakeholders would actually be necessary in their work. To introduce the WP2 and T2.1 to the partners better, numerous consultations and a workshop were organized.

During the initial months of the project, after numerous other activities and meetings, as well as after the project partners got to engage more in their activities, the context of the project and the need of SH involvement became clearer. With increased knowledge of the partners on stakeholders, the second stage of the SH mapping began – re-listing the stakeholders. The partners got a chance to re-evaluate such aspects as the need, importance, etc. of the stakeholders and update their primary wishlists. Some of the respondents were saying that no changes were made, others updated their primary version of the wishlist by adding few new stakeholders.

In the application form of the DISTENDER project there were 6 CCSs identified: Austria, Northeast of the Netherlands, Southwest Iberian Peninsula (Dehesas and montados), Guimaraes (Portugal), Gdansk, Metropolitan city of Turn. This list was updated in the early months of the project, when Gdansk core case study was shifted from the list of CCSs to the list of the follower case studies. Further in this project, the CCSs are referred excluding Gdansk case study.

T2.1 is based on stakeholders, their identification and role in the DISTENDER project. In order to determine the appropriate principle for approaching stakeholders, they were assigned to the outer or inner circle. The partners were asked to fill a stakeholder wishlist which is a template that has been created and structured according to a specific logic. Following the data gathered from the wishlists, the mapping stage was brought through as the stakeholders listed were set into separate scheme trees called stakeholder maps. As the T2.1 aims to help the partners (especially CCSs) identify their SHs, prepare them perform this themselves and propose the participatory methods and tools for the co-creation process, these topics are continued and implemented in these WPs: WP3, WP6, WP8 and WP9.

Based on stakeholder engagement matrix, the stakeholders were classified according to the four positions in the matrix: kept into account, kept informed, meeting their needs, and managed closely.

2.2 Stakeholder analysis and mapping

In general, the data that the core case studies have provided, varies in some aspects, such as the topic of case study, the type of their SHs, etc. Some of them were concentrating

towards external assistance, some of the representatives could not name the end-user at the initial stage of the project, etc. Moreover, the SHs listed by the CCSs are sometimes repeated but in a WP viewpoint, each SH shall be participating separately, according to the WP topic, hence the repeated SHs are not cancelled out (see the table 2 and annex 2).

Table 2: The distribution of the stakeholders according to the data provided by core case studies

	Austria (BMK)	North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)	Dehesas and montados (EURAF)	Guimarães	The Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)
Stakeholders identified	33	23	18	47	88
% of which:					
Contacted	3	9	5	55	59
End-users	9	0	0	19	24
Data providers	42	17	5	57	18
Expertise providers	18	43	85	15	19
Outer SHs	100	65	75	77	69

The Table 2 represents a quick review of the data received. It is important to note two aspects regarding this data:

- the number of stakeholders, weather it was large or small, is not a positive or negative thing as it just represents the possible actors that are or could be interested in the projects or its outcomes as well as can or could affect its outcomes.
- the SH wishlist is a fluctuating live document that is changing during and after the, depending on the levels of influence and interest of the SHs. Hence, some of the listed SHs might not be relevant in the future as well as new SHs might appear.

Figure 8: The DISTENDER stakeholders' co-creation and engagement scheme

In the figure 8 the interest groups interaction scheme of the DISTENDER is presented. It can be noticed that there are numerous engagement and co-creation activities within the framework of the project. CCSs, while working with inner and outer SHs, are at the same time SHs themselves in numerous WPs. The interaction between these partners is followed by the follower case studies (FCSs) with an aim to gain the know-how as well as the examples of the best practice.

Further in this section, each of core case studies are described in a more detailed way.

2.2.1 Case study 01: Austria (BMK)

The case study of Austria is the only case study of the national level. Austria is a federal republic with nine provinces, where competence for climate action can lie either at federal or provincial level, depending on the area. The new government formed a new Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology. Responsibility for spatial planning, building codes, land use and infrastructure permit procedures at provincial level. Austria's government has set itself the goal of being climate neutral by the year 2040. Fighting the climate crisis and reaching net zero emissions by 2040 in the transport sector is particularly challenging, as greenhouse gas emissions have risen by more

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than 70% since 1990 (except in the year 2020 due to the Covid Crisis). The entire transport sector has to undergo a socio-technological upheaval. The case study main interest is in infrastructure sector and related socio-economic and climate change related impacts.

Representatives of Austrian core case study have provided a wide list of stakeholders solely focusing on external ones: 33 stakeholders were listed in total. The stakeholders of this core case study are set in these work packages: 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 (see the figure 9). SHs that were evaluated as the ones having the highest level of influence and interest are written in the bold font in the scheme.

Figure 9: Distribution of stakeholders according to their dependence to work packages

According to the data provided, Austrian core case study has more than half (54% or 21 in number) contacts of the stakeholders mentioned and has already contacted one of them.

Regarding the circles of the stakeholders, Austrian representatives were concentrating towards external circle and for this reason all 100% of them are the outer ones.

All of the stakeholders listed are divided into end-users (9%), data providers (42%) and those who provide expertise assistance (18%).

Moreover, most of the stakeholders listed, according to the representatives of the Austrian core case study, are little or relatively interested in the project / it's outcomes as well as have

poor or average influence for the project. Those who are both, highly interested and the most influential for the engagement are these: 2 stakeholders listed have the highest level of influence for the project, but poor level of interest, 1 stakeholder has the highest level of influence and medium level of interest, and 4 stakeholders have the highest level of influence as well as interest towards the project (see the figure 10).

Figure 10: Distribution of stakeholders according to their interest and influence

Furthermore, Austrian core case study representatives have not identified any other category of stakeholders that would go beyond the usual boundaries of the internal and external stakeholder circles.

The Austrian CCS representatives named 2 SHs as the ones having the lowest level of interest but having the highest level of influence – this was the same SH identified as a science institution (The Federal Environment Agency), working in two different WPs – WP3 and WP5. Because of their low level of interest, there is a potential to the need to put more effort while working with these stakeholders. Moreover, it is evident that the number of the stakeholders, especially those who have the highest level of influence, is relatively small (7), which is why the “weight” of each SH increases accordingly. That means that as more stakes are put on each SH, the more carefully they shall be engaged, and the more work shall be dedicated to their engagement.

Regarding the stakeholders that, as evaluated, have both, the highest level of interest and influence, hence, shall be managed closely, separate mapping was performed (see the figure 11).

Figure 11: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

Furthermore, the stakeholders whose needs needed to be met were also mapped in the separate scheme (see the figure 12).

Figure 12: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

The SHs of the Austrian CCS are mostly of two fields: governmental (including federal bodies) or scientific (7 and 8 accordingly). Since the Austrian CCS is the only CCS in a framework of DISTENDER that is of national level, this distribution is corresponding. Since the significant part of the SHs are of national level, the engagement procedures could cause additional issues as the amount of any challenges as any sort of intervention would face higher level of opposition because there meet various interests and hidden stakeholders. Key Austrian SHs were listed as Umweltbundesamt – the environmental expert organization, Afsinag – highway infrastructure provider, SCHIG – the competence center for railways in Austria, OBB – Austrian Federal Railways. These SHs are named as crucial either in the WP8 or throughout all DISTENDER project (WPs 3, 4, 5, 6, 7).

In this case, the Austrian core case study could be characterized as the one where the stakeholders are usually proportionally influential as they are interested. This could mean that the core case study representatives have identified and influenced the essential players to have part in the project and be involved as much as interested throughout its process.

2.2.2 Case study 02: The North-east of The Netherlands (HUAS)

The case study 02 is specific as it is framed upon certain sectors (mostly energy and water) and then in relation to that also agriculture. It is a regional case study. To be aware of some legislative frames, that may affect the work in DISTENDER, the following note is mentioned: National environmental legislation (de omgevingswet, in Dutch), to be implemented in January 2023, requires integrated environmental management across sectors. Measures to integrate adaptation and mitigation interventions planned within the legislation are, for example, windmills on flood barriers and floating solar panels.

A list of stakeholders provided by representatives of The North-east of The Netherlands (shortly the Dutch) core case study was relatively balanced regarding internal and external stakeholders; 23 stakeholders were listed in total. The stakeholders of this core case study are set in the work packages: 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 11 (see the figure 13). SHs that were evaluated as the ones having the highest level of influence and interest are written in the bold font in the scheme.

Figure 13: Distribution of stakeholders according to their dependence to work packages

According to the data provided, The North-east of The Netherlands core case study has the contacts of 9 stakeholders mentioned and has already contacted 9% of all the stakeholders named.

Regarding the circles of the stakeholders, external one slightly dominates – 70% of the stakeholders are of outer circle.

The major part (46%) of the stakeholders is seen as the ones providing expertise, 17% are seen as data providers and none of the stakeholders were named in the role of end-users.

Moreover, the greater part of the stakeholders listed, according to the representatives of the North-east of The Netherlands core case study, are strongly or somehow interested in the project / it's outcomes as well as have strong or average influence for the project: 3 stakeholders listed have the highest level of influence for the project, but poor level of interest, the same amount of stakeholders have the highest level of influence, but average level of interest, and 14 stakeholders have the highest level of influence as well as interest towards the project (see the figure 14).

Figure 14: Distribution of stakeholders according to their interest and influence

The Dutch core case study representatives have not provided any other category of stakeholders that would go beyond the usual boundaries of the internal and external stakeholder circles.

The distribution of SHs of the Dutch CCS concentrates towards the right side of the graph what means that most of the SHs listed are influential. Moreover, because the level of interest is the highest of even 14 SHs, that proposes that the work with these SHs will be relatively fluid. Only 1 the most influential SH listed (Ports of Eemshaven and Delfzijl in the WP2) could be slightly difficult to engage because of average interest of theirs. On the other hand, no SHs in this CCS are identified as of low interest but the highest level of influence.

Regarding the stakeholders that, as evaluated, have both, the highest level of interest and influence, hence, shall be managed closely, were mapped separately (see the figure 15).

Figure 15: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

Furthermore, the stakeholders whose needs needed to be met were also mapped in the separate scheme (see the figure 16).

Figure 16: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

The North-east of The Netherlands core case study has elaborated that the external stakeholders are the ones that are difficult to refer to a particular work package.

The SHs of this CCS are mostly from scientific field (11) and this is partly because of the fact that part of them are internal SHs of DISTENDER project (e.g., modellers or partners from other CCSs). Another significant group of SHs is governmental / municipal authorities and representatives from such fields as water, farming and mitigation. Moreover, few SHs representing user / cooperation / connecting platforms and units were named. The core SHs of this CCS mainly are both, inner and outer: as inner SHs are name those partners who are participating in other CS (including the followers) or are highly important as the data providers. As the most interested and influential SHs are listed administrative provinces as well as regional water authorities that would be directly affected by the outcomes of the projects as well as would provide their expert assistance.

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2.2.3 Case study 03: Dehesas and montados (EURAF)

Dehesas in Spanish language and montados in Portuguese language, refer to a special type of cultural landscape. The case study 03 is specific as it is framed upon certain landscape typology which results from special agroforestry economy that reflects in land use. Therefore, the case includes parts of region Extremadura (Spain) and Alentejo (Portugal). Detailed information gathered in this chapter mostly refers to the Spanish case, as access to Portuguese stakeholders and data provides was limited at this stage. During the project this gap will be filled in.

Representatives of Dehesas and montados core case study provided a concentrated list of stakeholders which was dominated by external ones: 18 stakeholders in total. The stakeholders of this core case study are set in work packages: 6, 7, 8 (see the figure 17). SHs that were evaluated as the ones having the highest level of influence and interest are written in the bold font in the scheme.

Figure 17: Distribution of stakeholders according to their dependence to work packages; their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project (purple background in the lower right corner) and

according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project (dark green background in the lower right corner)

According to the data provided, Dehesas and montados core case study has the contacts of almost all of the stakeholders. However, regarding the approach itself, only 1 stakeholder (6% of all listed) was contacted already.

Regarding the circles of the stakeholders, external one strongly dominates – 75% of the stakeholders are of outer circle.

The major part (85%) of the stakeholders is seen as the ones providing expertise, 5% are seen as data providers and none of the stakeholders were named in the role of end-users.

Moreover, the greater part of the stakeholders listed, according to the representatives of the Dehesas and montados core case study, are strongly or somehow interested in the project / it's outcomes as well as have strong or average influence for the project: 15 stakeholders listed have the highest level of influence to the project, but average level of interest, and 1 stakeholder has the highest level of influence as well as interest towards the project (see the figure 18).

Figure 18: Distribution of stakeholders according to their interest and influence

EURAF representatives have not provided any other category of stakeholders that would go beyond the usual boundaries of the internal and external stakeholder circles.

The most of SHs of this CCS were mostly evaluated as having middle or high level of influence but only 1 SH of 18 were named to have the highest level of interest (inner SH of WP7 – scientific expert). This distribution may slightly challenge the communication as these stakeholders might be rather reluctant to get involved to the activities of the project. However, because of their numerous concentrations in the three, two, most of the SHs, have somehow similar viewpoint to the participation, hence, initial engagement shall be the same for all of them and later on the constant communication strategies shall be developed according to their actual engagement levels.

Having in mind a tight and concentrated distribution of stakeholders, the mapping of the stakeholders of this core cases study was performed accordingly – in one dimension: a stakeholder that gained both, the highest level of interest and influence and solely just the highest the influence, were mapped together (see the figure 17).

The SHs of this CCS are directly related with the overall orientation of the CCS – agroforestry. Half (8) of the SHs the CCS listed are somehow representing land managers / landowners or farmers, the others are mostly related with scientific field and others (NGO and a governmental representative). It is evaluated that the most interested and the highest level of influence has an internal stakeholder scientific expert. Dehesas and montados core case study representatives were short and clear regarding the list of their visible stakeholders, at the same time they had clear comprehension of the SH concept.

2.2.4 Case study 04: Guimaraes (GIUMARAES)

The case study of Guimaraes is the only case study representing the municipal level. A wide list of stakeholders provided by representatives of Guimaraes core case study was dominated by the external stakeholders: 47 stakeholders were listed in total. The stakeholders of this core case study are set in these work packages: 3, 4, 5, 7 (see the figure 19). SHs that were evaluated as the ones having the highest level of influence and interest are written in the bold font in the scheme.

Figure 19: Distribution of stakeholders according to their dependence to work packages

According to the data provided, Guimaraes core case study has the significant part of the contacts of mentioned (38 in number, representing 81%) and has already contacted more than half of them – 55%.

Regarding the circles of the stakeholders, external one dominates – 77% of the stakeholders are of outer circle.

The major part (57%) of the stakeholders is seen as the ones providing data, 19% are seen as end-users and 15% would provide the expertise assistance during the project.

Moreover, a relatively great part of the stakeholders listed, according to the representatives of the Guimaraes core case study, are strongly or somehow interested in the project / it's outcomes as well as have strong or average influence for the project: 7 stakeholders listed have the highest level of influence for the project, but poor level of interest, 1 stakeholder has the highest level of influence, but average level of interest, and 6 stakeholders have the highest level of influence as well as interest towards the project (see the figure 20).

Figure 20: Distribution of stakeholders according to their interest and influence

The Guimaraes CCS representatives have not provided any other category of stakeholders that would go beyond the usual boundaries of the internal and external stakeholder circles but have grouped some internal stakeholders of the WP4 and partners from WP5.

The SHs of Guimaraes CCS have been dispersed throughout the graph in a way that half of the SHs are not influential and interested along with a low influence level. However, some SHs are very influential but the level of their interest varies from lowest to highest. 7 SHs of this CCS are of the highest level of influence but the lowest level of interest: 1 inner SH (Wageningen University from WP3) and 6 outer SHs (Urban Management Division and INE in WP3, WP4 and WP5) is to be engaged with most of the challenges as their willingness to participate to the project might be difficult to induce. However, the determination to reach them out or engage to the activities will be necessary and their engagement activities shall be addressed accordingly – with high attention to their needs and details.

Regarding the stakeholders that, as evaluated, have both, the highest level of interest and influence, hence, shall be managed closely, were mapped separately (see the figure 21).

Figure 21: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

Furthermore, the stakeholders whose needs needed to be met were also mapped in the separate scheme (see the figure 22).

Figure 22: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

Since the Guimaraes CCS is at the level of municipality, a significant part of their SHs are of some sort municipal representation (e.g. municipal level divisions on such topics as green spaces, urban management, etc.), including a political body of municipal level – Guimaraes City Council. Major impact of SHs is seen through inclusion of inner SHs and scientific institutions. The highest level of influence and interest is also seen through the involvement of Guimaraes CCS team of representatives.

2.2.5 Case study 05: Metropolitan City of Turin (CMT0)

The metropolitan city of Turin is the most complex case in DISTENDER. It occupies a very heterogeneous territory, with significantly urbanised areas, from dense urban areas to small towns, but also incredible natural places, as well as considerable rural territories, spanning from the Alps to the basin of the river Po.

Representatives of CMT0 core case study have provided a wide list of stakeholders both, internal and external ones: 87 stakeholders in total. The stakeholders of this core case study are set in the work packages 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 11 (see the figure 23). SHs that were evaluated as the ones having the highest level of influence and interest are written in the bold font in the scheme.

Figure 23: Distribution of stakeholders according to their dependence to work packages

According to the data provided, CMTo core case study has at least one contact for each stakeholder mentioned and has already contacted 59% of all the stakeholders.

Regarding the circles of the stakeholders, external circle dominates – 69% of the stakeholders are of outer circle. All of the stakeholders listed are divided almost equally into end-users (24%), data providers (18%) and those who provide expertise assistance (18%).

Moreover, most of the stakeholders listed, according to the representatives of the CMTo core case study, are little or relatively interested in the project / it's outcomes as well as have poor or average influence for the project. 6 stakeholders listed have the highest level of influence for the project, but average level of interest, and 10 stakeholders have the highest level of influence as well as interest towards the project (see the figure 24).

Figure 24: Distribution of stakeholders according to their interest and influence

Moreover, CMTo core case study representatives have provided another category of stakeholders that represent not one person or entity, but group of stakeholders, e.g., citizens or territories. This type of stakeholders is a special one, as because of its nature of being a collective one, it cannot be engaged as a legal entity or a single SH – other strategies should be engaged.

As the CMTo has listed the most of SHs, there might emerge an additional challenge – the lack of resources to begin and sustain the communication between the CCS and it's SHs. As 59% of SHs of this CCS are already contacted, that leaves more time to address the ones that are yet to contact. However, having in mind forthcoming long-term SH engagement procedures, it would be beneficial for the CCS to efficiently relist or reevaluate their SHs and set the priorities for them to contact.

Moreover, the representatives of CCS of CMTo didn't identify any SHs that would have the highest level of influence but the lowest level of interest. That means that according to the first evaluation stage, no SHs would have passive attitude towards participation in the project. However, 6 highly influential SHs have the average level of interest (that are from outer circle and are mostly related with municipal / regional background) and more expedience as well as determination in approaching them could be necessary.

Regarding the stakeholders that, as evaluated, have both, the highest level of interest and influence, hence, shall be managed closely, were mapped separately (see figure 25).

Figure 25: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

Furthermore, the stakeholders whose needs need to be met were also mapped in the separate scheme (see figure 26).

As the CMTo core case study representatives have provided a detailed list of stakeholders, the maps which were made represents a widely spread net of the stakeholders that this core case study is planning to engage.

As the CMTo CCS is intensely heterogeneous, the number of SHs listed is accordingly numerous. The highest level of interest and influence of inner SHs is seen of expert of water and biodiversity. The other highly interested and influential SHs are the data providers (dominantly ARPA Piemonte), CMTo (as end-user and an expert) as well as the citizens as the providers of the expertise.

Figure 26: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

2.2.6 Inner DISTENDER stakeholders

Besides the representatives of the CCSs, the other project partners (representatives of all the WPs) were also asked to fill out the SH wishlist regarding stakeholders they identify from their perspective. The answers of the other partners of the project were gathered, merged and managed in one general map (see figure 27).

Figure 27: Distribution of stakeholders according to their highest interest and influence evaluations to the project

As it is seen from the map, majority of stakeholders named by other partners of the project are assigned to the inner circle (labelled green), hence, it means the other partners are concentrating towards internal processes and assistance as well as cooperation with other internal partners. This tendency falls in line with the fact that inputs and outcomes of the stakeholders mostly comes and circulates internally – within the partners of the project.

What is also evident, is that stakeholders of WP9 are dominating throughout the map. As the application form of the DISTENDER project refers, “WP9 is called “Case studies” and it targets to define the ecosystem of each case study where the other WPs will be applied; to support the successful implementation of DISTENDER case studies and final evaluation”. This dominant concentration of the interest and influence towards the stakeholders of the case studies means that other partners (underlining the follower case studies) are strongly interested in the processes of the WP9: understanding of the activities, problems, and the essence of the WP, is something other partners are interested in or feels that these stakeholders would be strongly important during or after their tasks as well.

The greatest interest of all the inner partners has been put on the CCSs, (they are the most relevant SHs of the project for them). This tendency goes along with the initial vision

proposed in the application form where the CCSs are the essential SHs in many ways – as the end-users, as data providers and experts.

In general, the data that all the partners and especially the core case studies have provided, varies in different aspects. Some of them were concentrating towards external circle, some of the representatives could not name the end-user at the initial stage of the project, etc. The number of stakeholders between the core case studies varied in the matters of number, field and influence.

The inner stakeholders of the project put the greatest interest on the core case studies (they are the most relevant SHs of the project for them).

3 Co-creation framework

This chapter is about the DISTENDER co-creation concept and its manifestation, including conceptualisation of stakeholders. Firstly, it enlightens some key and most often used terms in relation to collaborative processes, to spur reflection and discussion within the project. Secondly, it builds up a model for stakeholder involvement, focusing on processes of their identification, mapping and actual engagement. Then it focuses on co-creation approaches in relation to three key DISTENDER participatory driven activities: a. socio-economic scenarios, b. adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies, and c. the decision support system (DSS). To easily follow the practical steps of the DISTENDER co-creation concept which is also one of the subjects of this subchapter, an overview of case studies' participatory experiences and their experiences and familiarity with co-creative and participatory approaches and stakeholders' engagement is also summarised on the basis of DISTENDER product D9.1 Case studies. Finally, the co-creation plan over the key participatory related WPs is outlined.

3.1 Definitions

The concepts and approaches of participation, co-creation, co-design or related to stakeholders are very widely used – this pertains to different scientific disciplines as well as across the boundaries of science and public management. Even within the DISTENDER project, different approaches are proposed as regards e. g. the stakeholders and their roles, and the participatory methods and tools used. This should not come as a surprise since in the DISTENDER project integration at several levels is aimed for, such as between climate change adaptation and mitigation, sectors, or between scientific work and experience of case study partners.

In view of that, some recent definitions of the selected concepts are given in the following. They should not be understood as prescriptive but rather as “hypotheses” to be confirmed or otherwise in the DISTENDER project implementation process. In other words, the aim is to spur reflection and discussion within the project.

Four levels of definitions are used. The first one is definition of the term in a general dictionary of the English language. The rationale is that, when hearing the term, one usually recognizes it and connects the meaning with the general understanding of the term. One therefore believes to “know something” about the concept already. The second level of definition is Wikipedia as a rather well-known and much used source of (general) information. The third level are practice oriented sources, and the fourth level definitions found in the scientific literature.

3.1.1 Participation

In the Cambridge Dictionary⁴ the meaning of the term participation is explained as “the fact that you take part or become involved in something”.

Wikipedia connects the terms of (citizen or public) participation with social science. There it “refers to different mechanisms for the public to express opinions — and ideally exert influence — regarding political, economic, management or other social decisions. Participatory decision-making can take place along any realm of human social activity, including economic (i.e. participatory economics), political (i.e. participatory democracy or parpolity), management (i.e. participatory management), cultural (i.e. polyculturalism) or familial (i.e. feminism).”⁵

In an analysis of the recent developments with relation to the concept of participation in urban governance, Hedensted Lund⁶ mentions, among other, participation as a means to reduce inequalities of power in society, and as “a means of empowerment in order to support inclusiveness and participatory and deliberative democracy”⁷.

Generally, there is a notion that participation covers a range of different approaches and process characteristics. Rifkin et al⁸ indicate four stages, namely information sharing, consultation, collaboration, and empowerment. These are underpinned by model/process characteristics ranging from compliance/marginal participation, over contribution and collaboration/substantial participation, to (community) control/structural participation.

3.1.2 Co-creation

The Cambridge and Oxford on-line dictionaries do not contain definitions of the term co-creation. In the Wikipedia, on the other hand, a definition of co-creation is offered in relation to business⁹. It states that co-creation “refers to a product or service design process in which input from consumers plays a central role from beginning to end. Less specifically, the term is also used for any way in which a business allows consumers to submit ideas, designs or content... Another meaning is the creation of value by ordinary people, whether for a company or not.”

Ansell and Torfing (2021)¹⁰ propose the following definition: “Co-creation is a distributed and collaborative pattern of creative problem-solving that proactively mobilises public and private resources to jointly define problems and design and implement solutions that are emergent and seek to generate public value” (ibidem, p. 54).

⁴ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/participation>, accessed on 3. 2.2023.

⁵ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_participation_\(decision_making\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_participation_(decision_making)), accessed on 3. 2. 2023.

⁶ Hedensted Lund, D. (2018) Co-creation in Urban Governance: From Inclusion to Innovation, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323612706_Co-creation_in_Urban_Governance_From_Inclusion_to_Innovation, accessed on 17. 2. 2023.

⁷ Ibidem, p. 28

⁸ Rifkin, S. B. and M. Kangere, What is Participation, <https://asksource.info/cbr-book/cbr03.pdf>, accessed on 17. 2. 2023.

⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Co-creation>, accessed 17. 2. 2023.

¹⁰ Ansell, C. and J. Torfing (2021) Public Governance as Co-creation, Cambridge University Press.

The authors also state that “not all efforts at co-creation need to be or can be equally ambitious” (ibidem, p. 57) and propose a ladder of co-creation to accommodate the different objectives, scopes of participation, and intensity of interaction. The ladder has five levels, with the *first level of co-creation* consisting of gathering ideas, comments or feedback from users or stakeholders for limited and well-defined input into programme and service design. The input is gathered through crowdsourcing, focus group interviews, written consultations or public hearing. The interaction between actors included in the activities is limited.

At *level two*, users, citizens and stakeholder groups are engaged in focused design processes addressing specific problems or striving to achieve specific goals or tasks. They interact regularly but meet on a limited or ad hoc basis. Setting the agenda and steering the co-creation process is done predominantly by actors organising the process.

The *third level of co-creation* entails working with users and stakeholders while embracing more demanding formats such as innovation, problem-solving, or joint action. The input of users and stakeholders is significant and created over a longer time span. The basic agenda is still set by the actor organising the process, but the role is more facilitative and less directive. A deeper and more sustained dialogue among participants is needed.

At *level four*, “actors engage on an equal footing in agenda-setting aimed at identifying common problems or designing new and better solutions”¹¹.

Level five, finally, is characterised by co-creation becoming “reflexive” and a “wider ecology of co-creation” developing”¹².

3.1.3 Co-design

Definition of co-design in the Cambridge dictionary highlights that it is “to design something together with one or more other people”¹³.

The Wikipedia treats co-design as a synonym for participatory design. The latter is then defined as “an approach to design attempting to actively involve all stakeholders (e.g. employees, partners, customers, citizens, end users) in the design process to help ensure the result meets their needs and is usable. Participatory design is an approach which is focused on processes and procedures of design and is not a design style”¹⁴

In scientific literature, co-design is often discussed as part, or a type of the co-creation/co-production approaches, together with co-implementation and co-initiating. Generally, the three terms then describe the roles that the stakeholders have in the co-creation process¹⁵.

¹¹ Ibidem, p. 59.

¹² Ibidem, p. 59.

¹³ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/co-design>, accessed 17. 2. 2023.

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Participatory_design, accessed on 17. 2. 2023.

¹⁵ See e. g. Goličnik Marušić, B. and I. Šuklje Erjavec, 2020, Understanding co-creation within the public open space development process. In: Smaniotto Costa, C. et al. (Eds.): Co-creation of Public Open Places. Practice – Reflection – Learning, Edicoes Universitarias Lusofonas; Ansell, C. and J. Torfing, 2021, Public Governance as Co-creation, Cambridge University Press.

There are also other approaches focusing on co-design as a stand-alone concept. Kelly Ann McKercher¹⁶ argues that the “primary role of co-design is elevating the voices and contributions of people with lived experience. Beyond writing on sticky notes, co-design is about how we are being (our mindsets), what we are doing (our methods) and how our systems embrace the participation of people with lived experience (social movements)”¹⁷. As the four key principles for co-design, the sharing of power, prioritising relationships, using participatory means, and building capability are suggested.

3.2 Conceptual DISTENDER model for stakeholder identification and mapping

This chapter wraps up two main take-aways regarding stakeholders’ involvement, first focusing on preparatory activities for stakeholder identification and engagement, and second presenting interlinkages among the three key activities immanent to stakeholders’ involvement, from preparation to communication and implementation in a conceptual DISTENDER model for stakeholder engagement.

3.2.1 Stakeholder selection and mapping

Regarding the general view of the analysis and meetings with DISTENDER partners performed, the general view is considered that the partners (especially CCSs) tend to understand the SHs sometimes differently. Regarding the SHs of CCSs, external SHs tend to dominate. Only few CCSs have mentioned another category of SHs (collective ones) such as citizens, moreover, one CCS at the initial stage of SH mapping did not identify any internal SHs at all.

Regarding internal SHs of DSTENDER project, the understanding of SHs between partners usually also differs, mostly regarding concreteness of the SH as a unit. Moreover, it is notable that the concept of SH might differ across the project as well as different classification of the SHs might be applied. However, it is suggested to keep the communication between partners of DISTENDER as much consistent as possible, to acknowledge different understandings and classification of SHs in order to be aware of the intentions and interest of the partners / inner SHs as well as harmonize the understanding on the SH concepts.

¹⁶ Beyond Sticky Notes: Doing Co-design for Real, <https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5cc50b947fdcb81f7939668a/t/5efb116985126e27837f1622/1593512343569/>, accessed 3. 2. 2023.

¹⁷ Ibidem, p. 14.

Figure 28: SH identification and grouping stages

When a partner, CCS or a FCS sees the need to structure their SHs, there are 3 major steps to perform (also illustrated in figure 28):

- 1) Listing SHs. At this stage, the representative would think of possible SHs (whether inner or outer ones) regarding a specific topic represented and list them (SH wishlist). Initially, the list can be as much detailed as wanted – further evaluation is performed in latter stages. In DISTENDER project a specific topic will be always provided by the WP that covers the content of the participatory activity.
- 2) Applying criteria. This stage covers sectioning the SHs according to the SH engagement matrix (which is based by the criteria of evaluation the interest and influence levels of the SHs). According to the outcomes of criteria application, further engagement and co-creation strategies shall be applied. For each specific participatory activity within each relevant WP specific criteria will be assured within that WP, so the list of SHs will be as suitable for the purpose of the participatory activity as possible.
- 3) An update. During the ongoing project, some shifts in the SH wishlist might appear, e.g., new SHs might become relevant and be worth included to SH wishlist as well as some previously listed SHs (possibly) could appear not worth to be kept in the list anymore. In the first case, a new SH shall be analysed through interest-influence prism and structured accordingly. In the second case, where earlier listed SHs might seem not relevant anymore, it is suggested to keep them listed anyway (but visually muted) with an aim. This strategy is proposed because of changing circumstances (they might become relevant again) and to have them visibly listed (they have not been forgotten or looked through).

Further on in this section, the categories of SHs are discussed as well as the co-creation activities according to their grouping outcomes.

SHs to keep informed

The SHs that fall under the category “keep informed” usually tend to be characterized as the ones that have the highest level of interest but do not have abilities to be influential or affect the course or outcome of the project. However, despite the actual minimality of the influence of such SHs, it is suggested to keep a connection with them as their input might be useful in various ways as they would be interested in different types of assistance.

SHs to keep into account

The SHs that have the lowest levels of both, interest and influence regarding the project, although not being resultative, shall be acknowledged and not ignored. It is suggested to keep them in touch and update on the relevant processes ongoing but without expectations to get any relevant feedback.

SHs to manage closely

The category of SHs that is considered the most uncomplicated to engage and keep the contact with. They are to demonstrate the highest level of interest while being highly influential. They are the ones that is advised to keep satisfied, they shall be continuously communicated with and updated.

To meet SHs' needs

This group of SHs is highly important as well as slightly challenging as they, while being greatly influential do not have the same level of interest. This combination proposes that the needs of these SHs should be satisfied but the communication with them shall be carefully thought through because of their inertness towards the project. These SHs might be difficult to engage in the initial stages of communication and more careful contact is suggested to choose while communicating with them.

The co-creation activities shall also be applied depending on the topics of the activities and result wanted. The list of proposed co-creation methods and activities is provided in the annex 4.

As the stakeholder input is highly relevant during all the DISTENDER project, the stakeholder identification and mapping will also be present in the future. Hence, the stakeholder wishlist is a live document and partners shall be prepared to identify, classify, and map stakeholders themselves. According to the guidelines set in the D2.1 the partners will be prepared to implement stakeholder identification and mapping themselves.

3.2.2 DISTENDER framework for stakeholders involvement

In principle, the DISTENDER framework for stakeholders identification and engagement reflects three main slots of activities, preparation, communication and implementation, that can be detailed as follows:

- a) Identification of general topic upon which the stakeholders are going to be addressed, and related initial identification of possible stakeholders,
- b) Identification of specific question(s) that are the basis for each specific participatory activity,
- c) Set up criteria for wanted structure and shares of stakeholders to address the specific topic of the participatory activity as best as possible,
- d) Creation and finalisation of list of stakeholders requested for a specific participatory activity,
- e) Selection of the ways and media of communication with stakeholders,
- f) Early focused communication with stakeholders significant for the basic information about the planned event and about its expected term,

- g) Final invitation with the information providing the brief but exact information about WHAT, WHERE, WHEN, WHY, and HOW,
- h) Actual implementation of the participatory activity following the well-prepared process plan,
- i) After participatory communication activities.

Figure 29: DISTENDER framework for stakeholders involvement

Any participatory activity is related to the focused question upon which the participants discuss, share opinions, make further reasonings and the like. As often the participants may be invited into a series of chain events, where each event addresses new (but related) specific question, firstly, the broad topic, that covers all specific questions to be addressed in a series of events is identified (see step A in Figure 28), and a list of possible stakeholders can start to evolve. At this stage a structural analysis that results into groupings of stakeholders (as exemplified in sections 1.2.1 – 1.2.6 and described in section 1.3.1) regarding the way how to approach them in further communication is recommended. This analysis is for internal use for helping to shape the communication with stakeholders. A list of actual stakeholders that are invited to each specific participatory activity (e.g. face to face workshop) is then recommended to follow selection criteria provided by this participatory activity holder (see sub-section 3.2.1.1 Focused targeting illustrating The Prospex-CQI method as suitable for participatory activities of WP3 and WP6). Having the list of participants set up and a clue how to approach them, the actual engagement can start. This is also an action formed of several steps. An early invitation provides a main information,

the date and time frame of the participatory event, and clearly invites the stakeholder by showing his/her value in contribution to the topic addressed at the participatory activity. The means of communication is selected according to the most effective in each case study, and can also represent several options, from e-mailing to phone conversation. Final invitation keeps the key messages reflecting what the participatory activity will be about, where and when as well as for how long it will take place. Actual implementation of the participatory activity follows the well-prepared process plan, which at the event itself reveals detailed steps and activities of work as well as techniques or methods used (e.g., some of them are illustrated in 1.3.2). After participatory activity the participants are communicated again to receive e.g., thank you letter with take-away messages, invitation to further or related events etc.

3.2.2.1 Focused targeting

Stakeholders for the co-creation activities (i.e. main participatory event, such as primarily stakeholder workshops) will be selected based on the Prospex-CQI method.¹⁸ The Prospex-CQI method involves the following steps:

C = Criteria: Defining a set of criteria and categories for stakeholder groups that are either affecting or affected by the topic of research, or both.

Q = Quota: Setting specific minimum quotas for all categories.

I = Individuals: Identifying individuals that fit the categories, with the overall selection fitting the quotas set.²

The CQI-method allows the targeting of specific groups, expertise, sectors, or interests, depending on the objectives of a specific workshop. It also allows for the analysis of who was present and thus what quota were not met. Underrepresentation of certain aspects can lead to biased results, which could be corrected. In general, scenario development workshops aim at a broad participation across sectors, age groups, etc., while pathway development aims at a narrower selection of well-informed policy makers. In addition, DISTENDER aims at having a minimum of at least 50% stakeholders that attend all three workshops related to WP3 and WP6. This will all be taken into account when setting criteria and quota for each particular event.

There are the following categories for the criteria defined, based on societal groups that are affected by or affect climate change adaptation and mitigation (the research topic of DISTENDER), and the project objective O2, on vulnerable categories inclusion and avoiding the gender gap.

Topical categories include:

- Sectoral affiliation (subcategories include the key sectors for each case study, e.g. energy, agriculture);

¹⁸ Gramberger, M., Zellmer, K., Kok, K., & Metzger, M. J. (2015). Stakeholder integrated research (STIR): A new approach tested in climate change adaptation research. *Climatic Change*, 128(3), 201–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-014-1225-x>

- Institutional affiliation (subcategories include government, NGO (including grassroots), business, artists, academia).

Demographic categories include:

- Age (with the aim of including perspectives of youth);
- Gender (with the aim of including perspectives of women and avoiding the gender gap);
- Vulnerable groups (with the aim of including perspectives of minorities, including racial and ethnic minorities if applicable).

These are the overarching categories that will be used for stakeholder selection for each workshop in line with the topics of socio-economic scenarios and strategies. Precise quotas will vary based on the workshop objectives and case studies. For example, key sectors will vary by case studies, and the inclusion of stakeholders with different institutional affiliations will depend on the workshop objective. The precise quotas will therefore be outlined per workshop and case study in the relevant deliverables (e.g. D3.1 for the workshop on socioeconomic scenarios; D6.1 for the workshop on strategies). An example of the Prospex-CQI method can be found in Annex 5 exemplifying the stakeholder selection of the workshop on socio-economic scenario development.

3.3 Co-creation approaches

This chapter describes the main co-creation approaches and their characteristics intended to implement for a. co-creating socio-economic scenarios, b. co-creating adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies, and c. producing the decision support system (DSS).

3.3.1 Related to co-creating socio-economic scenarios

As part of WP3, DISTENDER will support the co-creation of socio-economic scenarios for each of the five core case studies, in order to develop a set of long-term plausible future outlooks of socio-economic factors until 2050. Specifically, a set of Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) will be developed for each core case study. These local SSPs will be based on existing higher-level SSPs, where possible at national level. European SSPs are also available.

Within DISTENDER the SSPs will be used in two distinct ways, involving different follow up activities. The first approach involves quantification of stakeholder-generated SSP narratives and translation into model input for a range of models, importantly land use. The second approach involves the use of SSPs to contextualise pathway development and robustness checking. These approaches have been used frequently and can be described as follows, as outlined in the report on Task 3.1, namely:

- a) Story and Simulation (SAS): In this ten-step approach qualitative socio-economic scenarios are co-produced by stakeholders and subsequently translated to model input. Model outputs of these stakeholder-generated scenarios can then be presented to and discussed with the stakeholders that developed them to increase consistency.
- b) Scenario planning: This is an approach that links qualitative socio-economic scenarios directly with normative pathways and/or existing policies, actions, and strategies. Model results can also be used here.

In the remainder of this text, the focus is on the scenario planning part of the work, which relates stronger to the co-creation framework. Methods to operationalise the Story-And-Simulation approach will be provided in D3.1.

The core methods are participatory scenario development workshops (one per case study), supported by preparatory webinars. There are two aspects that are key to consider for the workshops. First, there is a need for comparability across case studies. This means that there will be a set of “core SSPs” and “core scenario elements” (i.e. core sectors) that need to be included in each case study. At the same time, the diversity of case studies calls for a flexible methodology, with other elements able to be modified to fit case study characteristics. For example, the size of the case study can determine the appropriate workshop format (live or online), and the previous identification of existing SSPs in some case studies (Task Report 3.1) can allow for a methodology of adapting existing SSPs, as opposed to developing new SSPs from scratch in case studies where existing SSPs were not identified. A detailed description of the core methods and case study specific elements will be provided in D3.1.

3.3.2 Related to co-creating adaptation and mitigation integrated strategies

As part of WP6, DISTENDER will support the co-creation of integrated climate adaptation and mitigation strategies. The core methods are participatory workshops, supported by preparatory webinars. The exact details will be confirmed in discussion with the case studies and the wider work packages. The process will take place over several participatory events in each case study. In a first event, the focus will be on pathway development, involving the co-creation of visions of desired futures and backcasting to develop pathways to reach these visions. This will also involve the work from Task 6.2 in identifying current policies and actions. In a second event, the robustness of the pathways will be improved, by using DISTENDER results, including the WP5 modeling outputs and WP3 socio-economic scenarios. Similar to the development of SSPs, a flexible method will be employed with core elements (e.g. mitigation and adaptation policies) that will be decided later. A detailed description of the methodology will be provided in D6.1.

3.3.3 Related to producing the decision support system (DSS)

As part of WP8, DISTENDER will support the co-creation of DSS. The software design process of Decision Support System is already following a User Centred Design approach (UCD). It is a set of actions taken into account during the designing IT systems very much focused on the user, his needs and expectations. The user requirements gathering was the first stage of this approach and gathered information had its source in the actual needs, characteristics of the domain of application, and business processes performed by the users.

Determining the end-user groups and understanding their needs gave a basis for building of the concept how the system should be designed and what functionalities it should provide. The second stage of this approach will be the system design, concentrated on the results coming from the user requirements analysis and further consultations (to be conducted both with the partners and core case studies representatives acting in the name of the end-users). While user requirements answer to the question of what the system should be, the design stage will answer to the question how it should do it and what set of elements it will be composed of.

In order to implement the above, the following approaches, focused on participatory activities were defined where the DISTENDER already has supported or will support the co-creation process of the DSS development:

- organization of online meetings and consultations with both partners and end-users (e.g. meetings aimed at introducing to the subject of DSS, presenting the main assumptions of the discussed system in order to start the end-users' concept elaboration and sharing process focused on how the system could bring the value to a user, how to achieve a desired usability, what it could offer);
- conducting survey through a questionnaire dedicated to end-users, along with the presentation of the first draft of the mock-up of the DSS system use case;
- participation of partners and end-users in the use case mock-up development process,
- organizing meetings aimed at presenting, evaluating by the potential users and updating the developed DSS prototype.

Each of these activities has been (as part of WP8.1) or will be described in the relevant deliverables D8.1 and D8.2.

3.4 Overview of case studies participatory experiences

Based on the DISTENDER deliverable D9.1 Case studies, the case studies' experiences and familiarity with participatory activities is summarised below. There were several aspects commented, addressing case studies' experiences in participatory activities and their abilities regarding various steps required in participatory preparation process, addressing their assessment of potential stakeholders' readiness for participation as well as case studies' familiarities with participatory tools and the roles they may play in it.

Table 3 shows, that except the case of Austria, all other case studies have some experiences with stakeholders' participation, CMT₀ reported also that they have strong experiences with intra-institution participation, whereas other case studies were a bit reserved about that. The table also shows that the question of end-users shall in each participatory activity be well addressed or clearly defined, so the case studies will have no difficulties to define and contact them. More detailed information regarding each specific case study is available in D9.1 Case study, available at the DISTENDER Sharepoint repository.

Table 3: Cross-case studies readiness

Case study readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you have experiences with stakeholders' participation?	D/M NL	CMT ₀ GUIM	A
Are there experiences in intra-institution participation (collaboration between different departments)?	CMT ₀	GUIM D/M NL A	
Do you clearly identify which of the stakeholders are the end-users?	NL	GUIM D/M A	CMT ₀
Do you plan to perform communication yourselves or via specific other subjects and bodies?	CMT ₀ GUIM D/M NL	A	
Are there any specific limitations (from your side or a stakeholder's side) regarding the stakeholders your CS is willing to work, you are aware of?	D/M A GUIM	CMT ₀ NL	

A = Case study 01 Austria, NL = Case study 02 The NE of the Netherlands, D/M = Case study 03 Dehesas and montados, GUIM = Case study 04 Guimaraes, CMT₀ = Case study 05 Metropolitan city of Turin

Table 4 shows, that at the beginning of the project the case of Austria had no knowledge or information on stakeholder readiness, and that Dehesas and montados case study and the Dutch case study know their stakeholders very well. However, the activities within T2.1 and in other specific topics related DISTENDER activities where for various reasons contact with some stakeholders such as data providers, policymakers have been made and that knowledge on stakeholders in case studies is progressing.

Table 4: Cross-case studies assessment about stakeholders' readiness

Stakeholder readiness	YES	PARTLY	NO
Do you know your stakeholder's readiness for participation?	D/M NL	CMT0 GUIM	A
Is it easy for it to take action on an issue?		CMT0 GUIM D/M NL	A
Do you know your stakeholder knowledgeability?	D/M NL	CMT0 GUIM	A

A = Case study 01 Austria, NL = Case study 02 The NE of the Netherlands, D/M = Case study 03 Dehesas and montados, GUIM = Case study 04 Guimaraes, CMT0 = Case study 05 Metropolitan city of Turin

An overview of case studies involvement in participatory activities showed that they have experiences in taking different roles. In the DISTENDER all types of roles are relevant, so cross-sharing experiences can enrich the preparatory and implementation processes (see the Table 5).

Table 5: Cross-case studies' familiarity of techniques or tools for participation and roles taken in it

Case study involvement	Active participant	Preparation support	Organise/ implement
Workshop	CMT0 GUIM D/M	A	NL

A = Case study 01 Austria, NL = Case study 02 The NE of the Netherlands, D/M = Case study 03 Dehesas and montados, GUIM = Case study 04 Guimaraes, CMT0 = Case study 05 Metropolitan city of Turin

3.5 Overarching co-creation concept

Although each WP related participatory activities are following the specific targeted issues, backgrounded with the concrete process plans, there is an overarching co-creation concept that is a foundation for all DISTENDER participatory activities. There are three compounds of activities: main participatory events, supportive events that take place before the participatory event itself and can cover various technical preparations, clarifications and the like, and the activities that follow after the participatory event, which can address various open questions related to the participatory activity and its results. Figure 30 shows this concept and reflects also on the DISTENDER structure and shows which work package may predominately be involved to achieve results. According to DISTENDER project, WPs, that built greatly on the participation activities are WP3, WP6 and WP8, therefore Figure 30 illustrates also who is expected to be involved in any of the phases (before, at, after) of co-creation, and points out as well, that the system is open for inclusion any other partner or expert needed.

when?	before	at	after
what? what kind?			
who?	<p>WP2 + WP3 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP2 + WP6 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP2 + WP8 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p>	<p>WP3 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP6 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP8 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p>	<p>WP3 + WP2 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP6 + WP2 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p> <p>WP8 + WP2 + WP9 + <i>internal or external being recognised as essential</i></p>

Figure 30: DISTENDER overarching co-creation concept

3.6 Co-creation plan

The chapter outlines a provisional co-creation plan, which is based on the co-creation concept presented in Figure 30. A chain of preparatory activities supporting the main participatory event for each case study, the main event itself and then also the so called after main event participatory activities, is followed. The last item may be of key importance not only for the related participatory event but also as an input for any other work package or further tasks related to participatory activities (see Figure 5). The co-creation plan is based upon intra- and cross-work packages' related tasks. Special attention will be paid to inclusion of followers, as will be specified in documents of WP9.

Table 6: Template for co-creation plan development and currently known information

WPs/ Tasks	Co-creation activity title	Timeline	Main partners involved + tasks	Additional info
WP3, Task 3.3	Participatory event 1 per case study: Scenario development	According to PMP	WUR, UIRS, SC, UoC, alongside KVC and case studies: BMK, HUAS, EURAF, GUIMARAES, CMT0. <i>* tasks will be clearly stated in each process plan supporting the activity.</i>	Preceded by preparatory webinar; Optional follow-up discussions if needed
WP6, Task 6.1	Participatory event 2 per case study: Strategies & visions	According to PMP	UKCEH, WUR, U-Graz, alongside KVC and case studies: BMK, HUAS, EURAF, GUIMARAES, CMT0. <i>* tasks will be clearly stated in each process plan supporting the activity</i>	If needed: preparatory webinar and follow-up discussions
WP6, Task 6.3	Participatory event 3 per case study: Robust strategies	According to PMP	UKCEH, WUR, U-Graz, alongside KVC and case studies: BMK, HUAS, EURAF, GUIMARAES, CMT0 <i>* tasks will be clearly stated in each process plan supporting the activity.</i>	If needed: preparatory webinar and follow-up discussions

WP8, Task 8.1 + WP2, T2.1	Stakeholders identification and mapping: DSS as a final product of DISTENDER – a product for end-users	6th October, 2022	BMK, HUAS, EURAF, GUIMARAES, CMT0	Completed: already performed
WP8, Task 8.1	DISTENDER Decision Support System from the user's perspective	15th December, 2022	BMK, HUAS, EURAF, GUIMARAES, CMT0, SC, UIRS. Tasks/activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the initial mock-up, - a summary of the first user requirements collected in the survey - collecting the user requirements from the CCS representatives discussion about the next steps 	Completed: already performed
WP8 Task8.1	DISTENDER Decision Support System as a tool for the users	21 st December, 2022	UIRS, UniGraz, BMK, other partners Tasks/activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the updated mock-up, - collecting the user requirements from partners perspective discussion about the next steps 	Completed: already performed
WP8 Task 8.3	Validation of the DSS prototype with stakeholders	According to PMP	CCS representatives, partners <i>* tasks will be clearly stated in each process plan supporting the activity.</i>	If needed: preparatory webinar and follow-up discussions
Task 8.4	DSS Validation	According to PMP	CCS representatives, followers, partners	If needed: preparatory webinar

	<p>End-product should be tested by the followers at the end of the project; collected remarks/observations/ suggestion should be discussed * tasks will be clearly stated in each process plan supporting the activity.</p> <p>and follow-up discussions</p>
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1. Annex1: stakeholder wishlist template

WP	Partners	Inner circle								Stakeholders
		Name of a stakeholder (add numbers if needed)	Field of a stakeholder (e.g. public transport provider, science institution)	Has the stakeholder been contacted? (YES / NO)	Contacts of a stakeholder	Type of information required	Role of a stakeholder	Interest rate of a stakeholder (1- min, 3- max)	Influence rate of a stakeholder to the project (1- min, 3- max)	Comments
3	Partner (name)	1								
		2								
		3								
		4								
		5								
	Partner (name)	1								
		2								
		3								
		4								
		5								
	Partner (name)	1								
		2								
		3								
		4								
		5								
Partner (name)	1									
	2									
	3									
	4									
	5									
WP	Partners	Outer circle - EXTERNAL								
		* already known								
		Name of a stakeholder (add numbers if needed)	Field of a stakeholder (e.g. public transport provider, science institution)	Has the stakeholder been contacted? (YES / NO)	Contacts of a stakeholder	Type of information required	Role of a stakeholder	Interest rate of a stakeholder (1- min, 3- max)	Influence rate of a stakeholder to the project (1- min, 3- max)	Comments
3	Partner (name)	1								
		2								
		3								
		4								
		5								
	Partner (name)	1								
		2								
		3								
		4								
		5								
	Partner (name)	1								
		2								
		3								
		4								
		5								
Partner (name)	1									
	2									
	3									
	4									
	5									

2. Annex 2: Concise wishlist of CCSs

No	Name of SH	Field	Has SH been contacted?	WPs
BMK - Austria				
1	Umweltbundesamt - The Federal Environment Agency	Science institution	yes	3, 4, 5, 6, 7
2	Statistik Austria	Science institution	no	3, 4, 5, 6, 7
3	AustriaTech - Federal Society for Technology Policy Measures	Science institution	no	3
4	Austrian Energy Agency	Science institution	no	3, 4
5	ZAMG - Austria's state meteorological and geophysical service	Science institution	no	3, 5
6	Federal Minister for Climate Protection, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology Section VI – Climate and Energy	Governmental institution	no	4
7	BOKU - University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences	Science institution	no	5
8	Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Regions and Tourism	Governmental institution	no	5, 8
9	Austrian water management	Governmental institution	no	5, 8
10	Federal Water Engineering Administration	Governmental institution	no	5, 8
11	Federal Ministry of Internal Affairs	Governmental institution	no	5, 8
12	Fraunhofer Austria GmbH	Science institution	no	7
13	Vienna University of Technology	Science institution	no	7
14	SCHIG mbH	Governmental institution	no	8
15	Austrian Federal Railways	Public transport provider (railway)	no	8
16	Asfinag	Infrastructure provider (highway)	no	8
17	Representatives of federal subdivisions of Austria	Governmental institution	no	8
18	Austrian Automotive Transformation Platform - AATP	Stakeholder network for e-mobility	no	8
19	Transport operators (VOR, VST, OÖVV, SVV, VVK, VVT, VVV)	Governmental institution	no	8
20	ViaDonau	Waterway operator	no	8
HUAS				

D2.1: D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework WP 2, T2.1, 79
T2.2

1	Urbanisticni Institut Republike Slovenije	science institution	yes	2
2	Water Authority Fryslân	regional water authority	no	2
3	Water authority Hunze en Aa's	regional water authority	no	2
4	Water authority Noorderzijlvest	regional water authority	yes	2
5	Province of Friesland	regional authority responsible for mitigation	no	2
6	Province of Groningen	regional authority responsible for mitigation	no	2
7	Province of Drenthe	regional authority responsible for mitigation	no	2
8	Farmers organisation LTO-noord	farmers platform, prominent water users and polluters	no	2
9	Nature organisations (Natuurmonumenten/ staatsbosbeheer/ het Drentse landschap/ het Groninger Landschap/ landschapsbeheer Friesland/ It Fryske Gea)	nature organizations, prominent water users	no	2
10	Ports of Eemshaven and Delfzijl	two ports and energy hubs	no	2
11	Municipalities and villages in Friesland, Groningen and Drenthe	municipality	no	2
12	Local justice movements (e.g. Farmers Defence Force, Groninger bodembeweging)	citizens	no	2
13	Samenwerkingsverband Noord Nederland	lobby organisation for the NE of the Netherlands	no	2
14	Deltares	science institution	no	3
15	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL)	science institution	no	3
16	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut (KNMI)	science institution	no	3
17	Wageningen University	science institution	no	3
18	Goethe University Frankfurt	science institution	no	4
19	Universitaet zu Koeln/ University of Cologne	science institution	no	5
20	UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology	science institution	no	6
21	Valencia case study (follower) - Valencia Clima i Energia	science institution	no	9
22	Dehesa & Montado case study - EURAF	science institution	no	9
23	Fondazione ICONS	Science communication organisation	no	11

EURAF				
1	Expert of University of Extremadura	Scientific expertise	no	6
2	Expert of University of Extremadura	Scientific expertise	no	6
3	Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa	Science institution	no	6
4	Representative of Moinhos de Vento Agroecology Research Centre	Science institution	no	6
5	Scientific expert	Scientific expertise	yes	7
6	Farmer/Landowner	Farmer/Landowner	no	7
7	Farmer/Landowner	Farmer/Landowner	no	7
8	Farmer/Landowner	Farmer/Landowner	no	7
9	Farmer/Landowner	Farmer/Landowner	no	7
10	Development and Infrastructure Company	Land manager	no	7
11	Sociedade Agrícola do Freixo do Meio, Lda.	Land manager	no	7
12	Farmer/Landowner	Farmer/Landowner	no	7
13	ICNF - Institute for the Conservation of Nature and Forests	Land Manager	no	7
14	Extremeña de Protección e Investigación de la calidad del aire (REPICA)	Science institution	no	8
15	Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development, Population and Territory of Extremadura	Public institution	no	8
16	Heritage defense organization	NGO	no	8
Guimaraes				
1	Municipal expert	Municipal Works	yes	3
2	Energy expert	Energy	yes	3
3	Energy expert	Energy	yes	3
4	Landscape Laboratory	Environmental Education institution and Research & Development.	yes	3, 4, 5
5	Guimaraes City Council	Management Municipal Mobility and Transport Division	yes	3, 4, 5
6	Division of Green Spaces (DEV)	Management of all existing public green infrastructures in the Municipality	no	3, 4, 5
7	Vimagua	City Water Management and Supply Company	yes	3, 4, 5
8	Urban Management Division (DGU)	Urban and territorial management	yes	3, 4, 5

D2.1: D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework WP 2, T2.1, 81
T2.2

9	2030 Mission Framework	"sustainable development"	yes	3, 4, 5
10	Intelligent and Information Systems Division (DSII)	Municipal Division of Intelligent and Information Systems	yes	3, 4, 5
11	Municipal Civil Protection Service (SMPC)	Municipal civil protection service	yes	3, 4, 5
12	Economic Development Division (DDE)	Municipal economic development	no	3, 4, 5
13	Guimabus	Municipal public transport provider	no	3, 4, 5
14	APA	Portuguese environmental agency	no	3, 4, 5
15	INE	National Institute of Statistics	no	3, 4, 5
16	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	science institution	no	3
17	UPM	science institution	yes	4
18	GUF	science institution	no	4
19	UAVR - UNIVERSIDADE DE AVEIRO	science institution	no	4
20	The modelers	-	no	4
21	Partners from WP5 tasks (UAVR; NKUA; RDA; UoC; UPM; CEH)	-	no	5
22	RDA	Advisory boutique specialised in climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies.	yes	7
CMT0				
1	Planning expert	Spatial and strategic planning	yes	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
2	Air and energy expert	Air quality and Energy	yes	3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11
3	Mobility expert	Transport and mobility	yes	3, 6, 7, 9
4	CSI Piemonte	Geodata	yes	3
5	CMT0 Economic development Department	Economic development strategies at metropolitan scale	yes	3, 6, 7, 8, 9
6	CMT0 deputy Mayor	-	-	3, 6, 9
7	CMT0 Woman Councilor	with responsibility for economic development, production activities, tourism, strategic planning	-	3, 6, 9
8	Spokesperson for Homogeneous Zones of the CMT0	Spatial and Urban planning, development strategy at local level	no	3, 6, 8
9	Water and biodiversity expert	water and biodiversity	yes	4, 5, 9

10	Regione Piemonte	Spatial planning, water protection, biodiversity, energy, air quality	no	4, 5, 9
11	ARPA Piemonte	Local Environmental agency	no	4, 5, 6, 9
12	CSI Piemonte	Geodata	yes	4, 5, 9
13	CMT0 Councilor	environment and environmental surveillance, water resources and air quality, protection of flora and fauna, parks and protected areas, information system, board of directors and general affairs	-	4, 5
14	CMT0 Environmental department	Sustainable Development	yes	4, 8, 9
	IRES Piemonte	Sustainable Development/Regional plan for adaptation to climate change	no	4, 9
15	"ISPRA - Higher Institute for Protection and Environmental Research"	National strategy and plan for adaptation to climate change	no	4, 9
16	Spokesperson for Homogeneous Zones of the CMT0	Spatial and Urban planning, development strategy at local level	no	4, 11
17	CMT0 - Specialized function Protection of the territory	Hydrogeological instability and soil defense	no	5
18	Water and biodiversity expert	water and biodiversity	yes	6, 9
19	IREN	Energy and waste	no	6, 9
20	Ato 3	ATO3 is an association between 307 Municipalities, all included in the territory of the Metropolitan City of Turin, and the Metropolitan City itself. It represents the area to which the exercise of the responsibilities pertaining to the Local Authorities for the organization of the water service is transferred, including the planning of water infrastructures.	no	6, 9

D2.1: D2.1 Stakeholder identification, mapping and co-creation framework WP 2, T2.1, 83
T2.2

21	SMAT	Water management	no	6, 9
22	CMTo Natural Systems Department	Natural systems and parks	yes	6, 9
23	CMTo Councilor	with responsibility for the environment and environmental surveillance, water resources and air quality, protection of flora and fauna, parks and protected areas, information system, board of directors and general affairs	no	6, 9
24	CMTo Councilor	with responsibilities for territorial planning and soil defense, transport, civil protection	no	6, 9
25	Spokesperson for Homogeneous Zones of the CMTo	Spatial and Urban planning, development strategy at local level	no	6, 9
26	CMTo Territorial Department	Spatial planning strategies and instruments	yes	7
27	Spatial planning expert	Spatial planning	Yes	9
28	Order of Architects of Turin	Spatial and Urban planning	no	9
29	CMTo - Communication and relations with citizens and territories	Communication and relations with citizens and territories	-	9, 11

3. Annex 3: Concise wishlist of FCSs and inner partners

No	Name of SH	Field	Has a SH been contacted?	WPs
GOLEA (FLC)				
1	Environmental expert	environmentalist	yes	3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11
2	Environmental expert	environmentalist	yes	3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11
3	Energy expert	energetic	yes	3, 7, 9, 11
4	Energy expert	director and energetic	yes	3, 7, 9, 11
5	Finance expert	financial manager in Agency	yes	3, 7, 9, 11
6	Municipality of Nova Gorica	Department for environment	no	9
7	Slovenian Environment Agency	environmental data	no	9
Gdansk (FCS)				
1	Representative of Department for Environment	Department for Environment _ Municipality of Gdansk	yes	3
2	Manager of the biodiversity	Biodiversity unit - Municipality of Gdansk	yes	3
3	Air quality expert	Air quality research foundation	yes	3
DIPSTOR				
1	CEH	science institution	no	5
2	WUR	science institution	no	5
3	Uni Graz	science institution	no	5
4	UoC	science institution	yes	5
5	NKUA	science institution	no	5
6	UAVR	science institution	no	5
7	BMK	ministry	no	5
8	HUAS	education and research	no	5
9	EURAF	EU level association	no	5
10	CMT0	city/region administration	no	5
11	Gdansk	city administration	no	5
12	Guimaraes	City administration	no	5
UPM				
1	Environment and health expert	Environmental and health planning	yes	3
2	Mobility expert	Walkability and public transport	yes	3
3	Environment expert	Environmental planning	yes	3
4	Health expert	Heath planning	yes	3
UIRS				
1	WUR	Science institution	yes	2, 9

2	UKCEH	Science institution	yes	2, 9
3	ITTI	Enterprise/informatics	yes	2
4	BMK	National administration (ministry)	yes	2, 9
5	EURAF	EU level association	yes	2, 9
6	GUIMARAES	City administration	yes	2, 9
7	GDANSK	Municipal administration	yes	2, 9
8	HUAS	Education and research organization	yes	2, 9
9	CMT0	Metropolitan city administration	yes	2, 9
10	GUF	Science institution	yes	9
11	UOC	Science institution	yes	9
S2i				
1	Innovation expert	Innovation management & networks engagement	yes	11
2	NEVERMORE	HEU project	no	11
3	KNOWING	HEU project	no	11
4	Climate Chain Coalition	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
5	ETIP SNET	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
6	ETP ZEP	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
7	Global Bioenergy Partnership	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
8	Coalition for Energy Savings Plastics Europe	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
9	Bioenergy Europe	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
10	Spring Cluster	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
11	Assobioplastiche	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
12	EI – Energy Institute	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11

13	BBIA - Biobased and Biodegradable Industries Association	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
14	BBI-JU	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
15	BRENET- building and Renewable Energies Network of Technology	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
16	CEEweb Biodiversity	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
17	JCSS – Joint Committee on Structural Safety	Professional network in climate adaptation, mitigation measure addressing DISTENDER sectors	no	11
KVC				
1	EnergyCities	hubs	no	3
2	CLEPA	European Association of Automotive Suppliers	no	3
3	ICCT	International Council on Clean Transportation	no	3
4	ECF	European Climate Foundation	no	3
5	Research expert	Research institution	no	3
6	Climate Group	Climate Group	no	3
7	FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER	Coordinator of EU project NEVERMORE	no	3
8	Technology expert	Coordinator of EU project KNOWING	no	3
9	iCLEI	Local Governments for Sustainability	no	3
10	GOBAL CONVENANT OF MAYORS FOR CLIMATE AND ENERGY	Worldwide network of mayors	no	3
11	CONVENANT ON DEMOGRAPHIC CHANGE	Network of entities promoting age-friendly Europe	no	3
UB				
1	UoC - UNIVERSITAT ZU KOLN	science institution	yes	3
2	UK CENTRE FOR ECOLOGY & HYDROLOGY	science institution	yes	3
3	UNI GRAZ - UNIVERSITAET GRAZ	science institution	yes	3
4	UPM - UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	science institution	yes	3

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T2.2

5	AUSTRIA GOV	Public authority (public transport)	no	3
6	Dehesa & Montado	Public authority	no	3
7	North-east of The Netherlands	Regional water authorities	no	3
8	Gdańsk	Local authority	no	3
9	Guimarães	Local authority	yes	3
10	Turin	Metropolitan City authority	yes	3

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4. Annex 4: Overview of the participatory methods

Co-creation type / method	Description	When to use
Workshops	A short, intensive training program for a relatively small group of SHs, focusing specifically on techniques and skills in a specific area.	To receive input from stakeholders. The topic should be cleared out and the SHs should be carefully selected.
Brainstorming	A method of generating ideas and sharing knowledge to solve a particular problem, in which participants are encouraged to think without interruption. Brainstorming is a group activity where each participant shares their ideas as soon as they come to mind. At the conclusion of the session, ideas are categorised and ranked for follow-on action.	For individual as well as team problem solving. To use during workshops – the topic and question
Storyboards	To create a linear narrative through drawing and telling a story of a scenario in use.	To communicate essential information in visually appealing design. To be used to explain more complex processes and narratives.
Hackathon	Hackathon is a design sprint-like event in where project managers, researchers and other subject-matter-experts collaborate intensively on software-type solutions to a specific topic.	To engage in intensive collaboration over a short period of time. Due to their versatility as means to develop innovative ideas, add features to existing software, foster learning, tackle civic and environmental issues and build new or expand existing communities ¹⁹
Personas	Personas are (fictional) descriptions of a possible user or stakeholder based on a compilation of variables acquired	Used for representation of an audience which aid in the planning and

¹⁹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343735173_How_to_organize_a_hackathon_-_A_planning_kit

	through research. The personas can be applied in different circumstances and will help bring different perspectives based on the case/project.	development of communications. They ensure that the plan takes into account what these audiences might be thinking, feeling, seeing and doing, as well as how they like to communicate.
Journey map	An activity where one draws or writes the steps composing the outcome journey to identify the steps required to deliver the optimal result. The final map also aids in identifying aspects that might be lacking in the plan.	Tool to intimately understand what a stakeholder is trying to accomplish (their objectives and intentions) and the steps/actions/decisions that stakeholder needs to make to complete their journey.
Artistic Visualisation	This method entails presenting an image or drawing to introduce the workshop/meeting topic to inspire or provoke.	Usually to use in the early stages of a project to facilitate a workshop
Community Mapping	An exercise where participants identify the community stakeholders and create a map indicating how they relate and intersect with each other.	An important step in beginning the engagement process with persons of concern, used to better understand the trusted structures that exist in the community and their levels of influence
Empathy mapping	A tool to gain perspectives from project participants, stakeholders or users. It can create a collective perception on a solution our final outcome.	Used when wanted to 1) create a shared understanding of user needs, and 2) aid in decision making.
People value canvas	The tool supports stakeholders to gain insight into what people consider valuable in a structured way.	This process aids stakeholders and users identify key aspects of a solution / outcome

		<p>concepts and their value proposition.</p>
<p>World Café</p>	<p>In this activity, groups of 3–5 people gather around tables to discuss a common topic for a short time (10-15'). After the first round, a 'host' stays at the table, while the others move to another table. The host summarises what has been discussed at that table and the 'new' table participants share their previous conversations. This format allows for the threads of the various conversations to be linked together.</p>	<p>Used for hosting large group dialogue when: gathering collective intelligence on experiences or ideas around an issue generating new ideas collaboration and network building.</p>
<p>Reverse brainstorming</p>	<p>Reverse brainstorming is an activity focusing on developing bad solutions to the issue or problem giving perspectives on what the concept should avoid.</p>	<p>Used when:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) trying to solve more complex or deep-seated problems and: When people have trouble coming up with good ideas quickly; b) When people are stumped on how to solve a problem; c) When you want people to let go of their pre-conceived ideas about a topic; d) When you want people to step out of their comfort zone and find new ways to problem-solve.
<p>Idea dashboard</p>	<p>A way to create a visual overview of the co-created ideas and what they address. This activity facilitates the clustering and specific aspects that might need to be incorporated into the solution / decision.</p>	<p>Used when adapting or improving an idea. Helpful tool used during the brainstorming session.</p>

		It allows all participants to contribute to refining the idea.
Crazy 8	An activity where participants create eight distinct ideas in eight minutes. Very used as a way to kickstart an idea generation session.	Used for o generate as many ideas as possible within a short timeframe, focusing on quantity of ideas not quality, so at the end of the exercise, there are a ton of diverse ideas
Storytelling/video prototyping	This activity focus on creating narratives where the proposal is described within a context, its use and its purpose. It facilitates the sharing of an idea and it becomes easier to be understood by the other participants. It can be drawn or made as a video.	Used when more structure is needed, to draw in the audience.

5. Annex 5: Example of stakeholder selection based on the Prospex-CQI method

Category	Sector				Institutional affiliation						Demographics		
Criteria	Water	Energy	Agriculture	Health	Government	Scientist	NGO* (including grassroots/local NGO)	Artist	Business	Citizen	Age < 30 years	Gender = Women	Vulnerable groups*
Quota (minimum)	2	2	2	2	All that need to be present in follow-up workshops		2	2	2	2	2	At least 1/3 of participants	5
Stakeholder no. EXAMPLE: SH 1	X						X				X	X	X

